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Radar Echo Signals for Reconstruction

PARTICLE AND ASTROPHYSICS

MASTER THESIS PHYSICS AND ASTRONOMY

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Abstract

Cosmic neutrinos provide insight into the highest energy sources in the astrophysical environment. The Radar Echo Telescope is an experiment which aims to search for these neutrinos in the PeV - EeV energy range, bridging the neutrino flux gap between the upper end of optical Cherenkov experiments and the lower end of Askaryan radio detectors. The telescope plans to utilise radar techniques to detect ionisation trails left in ice. These trails originate from in-ice particle cascades produced in high energy neutrino interactions; therefore, their detection provides information on the progenitor neutrino. In this work, properties of the signal generated by radar detections have been investigated with the semi-analytic code **MARES**. An amplitude boosting effect has been identified and linked to coherence of the ionisation trail, for favourable geometries within the detector. A wide range of Doppler frequency shifts are also found, as well as Cherenkov effects that cause time-compression of the signal and strong frequency shifts. The signal properties exhibit good potential for use in methods to reconstruct the energy, arrival direction and interaction vertex of the progenitor particle, which has been explored in application for the Radar Echo Telescope for Cosmic Rays. Successful detection and reconstruction with radar signals in this experiment will pave the way for future use of radar techniques to help explore the high energy neutrino view of the sky.

Contents

1	Introduction	5
1.1	Cherenkov Radiation	6
2	Neutrino Astronomy	8
2.1	Motivation	8
2.1.1	Neutrino Properties	11
2.2	Neutrino Telescopes	13
2.2.1	Building Neutrino Telescopes	13
2.2.2	Status Today	14
2.2.3	RET-N	16
3	Radar and Air Showers	20
3.1	Radar Detection of Particle Cascades	20
3.1.1	Air Showers	20
3.1.2	In-Ice Particle Cascades	21
3.2	The RET-CR Test Beam	22
3.3	The RET-CR Deployment	25
4	Methods	29
4.1	MARES	29
4.2	Approach	31
4.2.1	Simulation Detector setup	31
4.2.2	Signal Properties	34
4.3	Mapping Methods	40
5	Signal Properties	44
5.1	Plasma Coherence	49
5.1.1	Amplitude	49
5.1.2	Frequency	55
5.2	Cherenkov Effects	58
5.3	Summary	67
6	Reconstruction	68
6.1	Reconstruction Goals	68
6.1.1	Energy	68
6.1.2	Arrival Direction	69
6.1.3	Interaction Vertex	70
6.2	Position Reconstruction Methods	71

6.2.1	Trilateration	71
6.2.2	Interferometry	74
6.3	Summary	77
7	Conclusion	78
7.1	Discussion	78
7.1.1	Future Work	80
7.2	Outlook	81
A	Extended Analysis	83
A.1	Further Signal Properties	83
A.1.1	Antenna Distance	83
A.1.2	Antenna Depth	84
A.1.3	Transmitter Frequency	85
A.1.4	Polarisation	86
A.1.5	Energy	87
A.1.6	Refractive Index	88
A.1.7	Plasma Lifetime	89
A.1.8	Phase plots	90
A.2	Position, Antenna Depth and Transmitter Frequency	91
B	Research Data Management	96
C	Acknowledgments	97

Chapter 1

Introduction

Figure 1.1: Diagram of the Radar Echo Telescope for Cosmic Rays (RET-CR). Retrieved from [1].

A high energy neutrino interacting in ice produces a cascade of relativistic particles. As the cascade propagates it ionises the surrounding ice, leaving behind a short-lived, dense trail of charge that will be referred to as a plasma. At sufficient densities, this plasma is capable of scattering incident radio frequency radiation, produced by a transmitter situated into the ice. The scattered radiation will form a radio echo that can be detected in a receiver, and analysed to retrieve properties of the plasma and high energy particle that produced it. This is the mechanism of the radar echo signal, which forms the basis of the method that will be employed by the Radar Echo Telescope (RET) experiment to detect high energy astrophysical neutrinos.

The work undertaken in this thesis is motivated by the need to gain a better understanding of this scattered radar signal. This represents a new detection method for high energy particles in ice, and as such we are left with lots of avenues to explore how this signal

presents. It has been shown that the combination of the transmitter, relativistic cascade, reflecting plasma and receiver in three-dimensional space leads to a range of complexities in the produced signal, compounded by additional medium-specific intricacies. Untangling these effects presents a challenge, but once a thorough understanding of the signal and its properties has been achieved, it can be employed in reconstruction methods to gain information on the progenitor particle. The accuracy and precision of reconstruction methods are important in any (neutrino) telescope, and disentangling the various different effects seen in the signal properties should provide many possible options with which to approach this reconstruction, leading to accurate and efficient techniques.

Specifically, the reconstruction potential of signal properties has been explored in application to the Radar Echo Telescope for Cosmic Rays (Fig. 1.1), situated in Greenland. This experiment is designed to demonstrate detection of the radar echo signal in-situ, as well as developing the necessary triggering programs and technology required to eventually detect neutrinos. Instead of detecting in-ice cascades produced by neutrinos, it instead searches for the secondary in-ice cascades generated by cosmic ray air showers impinging on the ice surface. The profile of the plasma produced by these two mechanisms are very similar; therefore, detecting the air showers in-ice cascades allows for the radar method to be validated and the radar echo signal to be explored.

The aim of this thesis therefore is to identify and explore properties of the radar echo signal. These properties can then go on to be utilised in future reconstruction methods for the radar detection of high energy particles. In order to do this, the code package **MARES** was used. This was created in the course of the PhD work of Enrique Huesca Santiago, and forms the basis of the signal analysis within, allowing for radar echo signals from many possible events within the framework of the RET-CR experiment to be generated and investigated. Properties of the signals from these events have been explored and some interesting mechanisms have been identified, concluding with discussions of the properties in the context of possible reconstruction methods.

Chapters 2 and 3 will explore relevant scientific background to the radar echo signal and the RET experiment, including the motivation behind neutrino astronomy, past radar experiments searching for air showers, the profile of in-ice cascades and the recent work leading to the new application of radar techniques to in-ice neutrino cascades. This will be followed by a description of the approach undertaken in this work, in Chapter 4. The results produced by this approach for the properties of the radar echo signal are detailed in Chapter 5, and in Chapter 6, these properties are discussed in context of their application towards potential reconstruction methods. Conclusions and possible future work are then discussed in Chapter 7.

1.1 Cherenkov Radiation

Before properly exploring the background of this work, we will briefly introduce a phenomena that appears in a variety of different forms throughout the following chapters; Cherenkov radiation.

Figure 1.2: Cherenkov radiation, emitted according to the blue arrows at the angle at which coherence of the wavefront is achieved. The Cherenkov angle θ_c is marked in red.

Charged particles propagating through a medium, at velocities higher than the speed of light in that medium, will emit Cherenkov radiation in the form of photons, shown in Fig. 1.2. This is caused by the coherence found in the fields of the moving charged particle, which constructively interfere at a particular axis opening angle - the Cherenkov angle θ_c . This angle depends on both the particle speed and the properties of the propagation medium, described in Eq. 1.1. Accordingly, the maximum angle of radiation will be found for particles travelling at $\beta \sim 1$.

$$\cos \theta_c = \frac{1}{n\beta} \quad (1.1)$$

Cherenkov effects are in fact found in the emission produced both by the relativistic motion of charged particles, as well as that produced by fast-moving electric currents [2]. Examples of this are seen in cosmic ray air showers; atmospheric Cherenkov emission is produced, with optical photons created in a forward-directed cone, primarily produced by the relativistic cascade electrons and muons [3]. Another example is found in the air shower radio emission, where it leads to time compression of the radio signal. This is seen as distinct time profiles with a branch point corresponding to the time of Cherenkov emission [2, 4]. And at this region, the energy of the radio pulse scales quadratically with the number of shower particles, boosting the signal amplitude.

Cherenkov effects are also seen in the in-ice particle cascades generated by neutrinos; where radio emission is again generated as a product of coherence over the length of the cascade. For emission to be coherent, the wavelengths under consideration must be longer than the typical dimensions of the cascade, which affects the frequency of the Cherenkov emission produced [5]. Therefore, the effects in both these emission mechanisms are dependent on the coherence of the electromagnetic emission; if this condition is met, we can expect the appearance of Cherenkov effects.

Chapter 2

Neutrino Astronomy

Neutrino astronomy studies the high energy neutrinos produced in the surrounding galactic and extragalactic environment - cosmic neutrinos - in order to better understand the energetic processes producing them; just as optical observatories have been doing with photons for several hundred years. Neutrinos have been found to exhibit certain properties that make them particularly compelling targets for astronomy. Yet successfully detecting neutrinos presents a swathe of experimental challenges which must be overcome; largely because of their extreme reluctance to interact with any materials on Earth. Up until 2013, cosmic neutrinos had only been successfully located from two sources: a relatively nearby supernova, and the sun. In recent years however, more detections have been reported by large-scale neutrino telescopes, and these detections have shown that it is possible to obtain both large enough event numbers and feasible angular resolution with which to perform astronomy. To achieve this, large-scale detectors across the planet are currently undergoing development with the aim of producing much higher event numbers across the entire sky. However, the aim is also to retrieve events for as wide a range of energies as possible, which requires new detection techniques and developments, including the Radar Echo Telescope experiment. The aim of this chapter is to provide a brief introduction to the field of neutrino astronomy; motivation, history and current status, culminating with the role of RET within that field, and the unique properties of the experiment.

2.1 Motivation

The detection of cosmic neutrinos provides access to a rich channel of information on both fundamental particle physics and a range of high-energy astrophysical processes. In practice, this involves successfully recording neutrino interaction events, and then identifying particular observable features in each event: their arrival times on Earth, energies, flavour composition and arrival directions [6]. Analysing these observables provides insight into the physical conditions found at the neutrino sources and surrounding environments, as well as into the neutrinos themselves. In Fig. 2.2, neutrino spectra are compared for range of dominant neutrino sources. Cosmic neutrinos, heralding from any location beyond and including the sun, can be found at energies as low as $\sim \text{keV}$ ¹. Neutrino astronomy largely focuses on energies $> \text{GeV}$, where we expect to see significant contributions from galactic

¹Cosmological, or relic neutrinos are found at much lower energies and should, by definition, be included in the category of cosmic neutrinos, but their detection represents a significantly different challenge (e.g [7]). Therefore, they are not included in subsequent discussions.

and extragalactic sources - of clear interest to astronomers. Furthermore, the target neutrinos beyond this threshold have significant enough energy to enable measurements of their arrival directions. As an interesting aside, this last point often represents the difference between neutrino detectors, which are not designed to provide directional data, and neutrino telescopes, which need to be able to establish neutrino arrival directions, in order to help identify their sources on the sky [8]. For clarity, throughout this work the energy categories of [6] will be followed, with high energy (HE) neutrinos found between TeV - PeV energies, and ultra high energy (UHE) neutrinos $>$ PeV. To illustrate some of the varied potential physics from neutrinos of these energies, we will investigate the major areas of motivation in further detail.

Figure 2.1: A selection of possible neutrino sources. From left to right: The supernova remnant Cassiopeia A imaged with JWST (NASA, ESA, CSA, D. Milisavljevic, T. Temim, I. De Looze, J. DePasquale); the relativistic jet from M87, in optical and IR light (NASA, ESA and the Hubble Heritage Team (STScI/AURA); P. Cote and E. Baltz.); the Centaurus A galaxy, produced with a combination of radio, X-ray and optical wavelengths (ESO/WFI (Optical); MPIfR/ESO/APEX/A. Weiss et al. (Submillimetre); NASA/CXC/CfA/R.Kraft et al. (X-ray)), and the remnant of the core-collapse supernova SN1987A, also imaged with JWST (NASA, ESA, CSA, M. Matsuura, R. Arendt, C. Fransson, J. Larsson, A. Pagan).

- *Insights into fundamental physics.* The observables of cosmic neutrinos are expected to be encoded with signatures of possible new physics mechanisms. Flavour mixing, neutrino HE cross-sections and mass ordering parameters all represent properties that can be investigated with a large pool of neutrino events, helping provide limits to beyond the standard model scenarios; sterile neutrinos, neutrino-self interactions, neutrino decay, and more, as has already been achieved with neutrino oscillations [9]. Furthermore, the energies reached by cosmic neutrinos are significantly higher than can be feasibly be produced on Earth, allowing useful comparison to known parameters established in lower energy experiments.
- *Astrophysical neutrino sources.* Neutrinos are expected to be produced in a range of high energy astrophysical phenomena (Fig. 2.1) both in our galaxy from supernova remnants and interactions with the galactic plane interstellar medium, and beyond it; blazars in active galactic nuclei, and gamma ray bursts from stellar collapses or binary mergers [10]. This often includes sources that have been studied in other observational channels, with theoretical and simulation-based research providing reasonable evidence

that the processes producing emission in other channels will also generate neutrinos - if only they can be identified. Spotting these neutrinos is particularly useful since they point back to their sources, and carry a lot of information about the conditions found there. In conjunction with other messengers (electromagnetic photons, gravitational waves, cosmic rays) this produces a much fuller picture with which to try and untangle the mechanisms behind these phenomena.

- *Highest energy accelerators.* Measurements of cosmic rays found on Earth have shown that they can exhibit extreme energies, $> 10^{20}$ eV, e.g. [11]. However, the origin of these energetic cosmic rays, and the processes that lead to their acceleration through space have historically proved elusive and are currently not well understood. It has been established that cosmic rays sources likely also produce neutrinos, as byproducts of high energy cosmic rays interacting with matter or radiation. This occurs through pion production followed by hadronic decay processes, generating neutrinos which carry a proportion of the progenitor cosmic ray energy. An example production channel of proton - matter interactions is shown below (Eq. 2.1), leading to a range of neutrinos and antineutrinos [12]. The link between the two messengers means that detecting and locating the source of very energetic neutrinos will also point towards the cosmic ray accelerators [13].

Unfortunately, the task of detecting cosmic neutrinos has proven challenging, for a particular reason; as demonstrated in Fig. 2.2, high energy neutrinos have very low fluxes, making them hard to detect on Earth. At higher energies especially, this quickly becomes a major limiting factor in the success of neutrino astronomy. Any neutrino telescope hoping to operate successfully has to overcome this low flux, searching for rare neutrino events that are often buried in dominant background signals in order to obtain reasonable numbers of events with which to perform astronomy. Consequently, this helps explain why the entire catalogue of cosmic neutrino source detections - up until recent years - contained only two detections, which poses some issues in demonstrating the feasibility of neutrino astronomy. Luckily, at lower energies the neutrino flux rate represents a less significant impediment, and accordingly more discoveries have so far been achieved. Therefore, the next section will explore the current known neutrino parameters, how they are expected to apply to HE astronomy and how they have already been utilised at lower energies.

Figure 2.2: Measured and predicted flux spectra for the dominant neutrino sources across possible energies. Retrieved from [12].

2.1.1 Neutrino Properties

Neutrinos are elusive, electrically neutral fermions with very small cross sections, interacting only via the weak (and gravitational) interactions, rarely influencing their surroundings and ignoring both the electromagnetic and strong interactions. They can be found in both particle and antiparticle form, and have been shown to oscillate between three different flavour eigenstates (ν_e, ν_μ, ν_τ). These flavour eigenstates are in fact superpositions of three mass eigenstates, meaning that neutrinos defy Standard Model predictions to indeed exhibit masses, albeit at very small values. If we place these properties in an astrophysical context, they become very useful. For example, once neutrinos are produced in acceleration or decay mechanisms, their small interaction cross-sections mean that they are free to escape from very dense environments that may be inaccessible to photons. Once released, their paths are not bent by magnetic fields, as cosmic rays are, or affected by absorption, unlike photons at high energies, allowing them to travel relatively unimpeded in straight lines. Therefore, establishing the arrival direction of a detected neutrino provides a reliable indicator of the sky position of the source that produced it. This is an important point for the identification of ultra high energy cosmic ray (UHECR) accelerators; while neutrinos are not easier to detect, once they have been, they indicate the location of their sources. This is a property shared by gamma-rays, which are also expected to be produced during CR acceleration processes. However, HE gamma-rays² are produced through multiple production channels; via neutral pion decay, but also through inverse Compton scattering and synchrotron radiation. Conversely, neutrinos can only be produced through hadronic decays, signalling the presence

²Gamma-rays also suffer absorption past certain energy thresholds, limiting the extent of their energy spectrum [8].

of accelerated CRs and making them an ideal detection channel for UHECRs. The production mechanisms described in Fig. 2.1 generate neutrinos with energies of $\sim 3 - 5\%$ of their progenitor energy. Therefore, a PeV neutrino source will enable the study of ~ 100 PeV CRs, around the transition from the galactic to extragalactic CR spectrum [6]. Furthermore, on arrival at Earth neutrinos carry a significant amount of information about the source that produced them. Their expected arrival flavour composition - the relative amounts of each neutrino flavour - from oscillations is $\approx 1:1:1$ (e, μ, τ), averaging over large-scale distances. However, in sources with particularly extreme environments i.e strong magnetic fields or high energy densities [14, 15], particular neutrino production mechanisms can be suppressed or influenced, leading to a modified flavour ratio on Earth. Constraining these differences allows for rates of particular production mechanisms to be estimated, and limits on their physical conditions to be established.

The hadronic acceleration mechanisms expected to produce neutrinos (among various other forms of emission) have been theorised to occur in a wide range of astrophysical phenomena; active galactic nuclei (blazars), gamma ray bursts, supernova remnants, starburst galaxies and many others, with neutrino emission varying from transient to steady point, extended or diffuse sources, all of which contribute to the expected cosmic neutrino flux on Earth. For example, CRs interacting with the large concentration of interstellar matter found in the galactic plane are expected to produce a steady diffuse neutrino flux. Gamma-ray bursts, on the other hand, are expected to accelerate electrons and protons along shock fronts formed from the ejecta, leading to a transient neutrino burst. For many of these sources, limits for neutrino flux contributions and energies have been theorised or simulated, but identifying sources will require directional neutrino events, ideally with significant statistics or with other messenger observations to help confirm the nature of the source.

While HE neutrino data is still relatively sparse, at lower energy ranges (sub-TeV) neutrino detections and experiments have been completed for a comparatively long time, leading to a host of new physics discoveries. This includes the experimental work towards the first solar neutrino detections, undertaken by groups including the Homestake experiment, SAGE and Kamiokande detectors [16]. The performed measurements confirmed the presence of fusion reactions in the sun, and with the addition of the Sudbury Neutrino Observatory (SNO), allowed for the solar neutrino problem - a deficit in the measured solar flux compared to the expected models - to be identified and later solved, demonstrating neutrino flavour oscillation for the first time.

Another example is the detection of neutrinos from the SN1987A core-collapse supernova, also shown in Figures 2.1 and 2.2. Neutrinos play an integral role in the core-collapse mechanism, carrying away $\sim 99\%$ of the explosion energy in a huge burst of ~ 10 MeV energy neutrinos that then flood the Earth for a brief period of time. The progenitor star Sanduleak -69 202 was located over 50 kiloparsecs away in the Large Magellanic Cloud, and the explosion was estimated to have produced $\mathcal{O}(10^{57})$ neutrinos. However even with this large number, detectors at the time were only able to spot two dozen correlated events³. Despite this, data from the detections proved remarkably useful both for placing valuable limits on

³The exact number of detected neutrinos varies significantly, as does the number of detectors that made the measurements. General consensus agrees that both the Kamiokande and IMB detectors made successful detections, while the Baksan and Mont Blanc reports are less certain [17].

neutrino properties (electric charge, magnetic moment, lifetime, mass) and for providing new insights into the core-collapse mechanism itself [18]. This is another area where neutrino properties come into play; they are able to escape from the dense stellar core while photons are blocked, meaning that this represented a unique opportunity for astronomers to gain insight into the core dynamics [19].

2.2 Neutrino Telescopes

The expectations for neutrino astronomy at high energies have been explored, and supported with the successful experiments at lower energies. The remaining step then is to discuss the detection process itself; the challenges faced and overcome in the last sixty years in order to build neutrino telescopes, and how that has led to the following generation of telescopes, including RET.

2.2.1 Building Neutrino Telescopes

Neutrinos are not detected directly. Instead, their interactions with matter produce various types of emission which is observed and used to infer properties of the progenitor neutrinos. For example, a muon neutrino interacting with a neutron via the weak interaction produces a relativistic muon. The muon then propagates at speeds greater than the speed of light in the medium, generating optical Cherenkov photons which can be recorded with photomultiplier tubes (PMTs). This is the basic detection concept described in 1960 by Markov [20], with astronomy applications and potential also explored independently by Greisen [3] and Reines [21]. Subsequently, the DUMAND⁴ group began meeting in 1975 [22], producing the first tangible designs for a neutrino telescope. The DUMAND detector planned to uniformly attach PMTs to strings anchored in the ocean off the coast of Hawai'i, utilising the Pacific ocean as the target medium. Unlike traditional optical telescopes, neutrino detections make use of a large, transparent medium for the neutrino to interact in, and choosing a naturally occurring medium (water, ice, rock) reduces expense. However, there are also other factors to consider when choosing a target medium; low event rates and high noise backgrounds.

The low neutrino interaction rates made it clear that in order to obtain statistically significant numbers of events, the detector would have to be large, ideally on the scale of cubic kilometres. At the time of DUMAND, knowledge of neutrino properties was relatively sparse since they themselves were very new particles. Consequently, determining exactly how big a detector to build, and establishing the sensitivity of that detector was difficult [23]. The ocean was therefore an attractive prospective medium, since building in the Pacific would allow flexibility in the size of the large scale structure needed. Furthermore, there was the secondary benefit that the effective size of the detector would naturally be increased, since interactions from the surrounding material could also be measured, increasing the event rate.

The other significant factor needed to be accounted for were noise backgrounds. These can be specific to a medium - bioluminescence from plankton and fish in water, or frozen bubbles in ice - or more universal, such as atmospheric muons. The latter is an especially significant background for optical Cherenkov telescopes, where muons represent the primary

⁴Deep Underwater Muon and Neutrino Detector

neutrino detection channel. Therefore, any telescope hoping to see cosmic neutrinos requires shielding from this atmospheric muon flux to reduce the background to more manageable levels. Past neutrino experiments at lower energies (SNO, Homestake) diminished this effect by positioning themselves in underground mines, where the rock layers above reduced the energy of incident muons, minimising the backgrounds. Possibly due to the larger size of the telescope, DUMAND instead chose to utilise the deep ocean, employing the water above as effective muon shielding.

Over the next ten years or so, the design of DUMAND underwent several downsizes to smaller and smaller volumes due to cost and building constraints; unfortunately in 1995 funding for the project was stopped completely [24]. However, the detection concept was not abandoned; the BDUNT/NT-200⁵, NEMO⁶, NESTOR⁷ and ANTARES⁸ collaborations operated largely in the following years, exploring the feasibility of water neutrino detection [25–28]. The BAIKAL NT-200 detector, located in the deep fresh water Lake Baikal, was the first neutrino telescope to successfully detect atmospheric neutrinos. NEMO, NESTOR and ANTARES all aimed to instrument an area of the deep Mediterranean sea, and ANTARES successfully detected neutrinos for fourteen years, producing a sizable event dataset still being analysed today [29, 30]. Meanwhile in the southern hemisphere, a different approach was conceived with the AMANDA⁹ project [31]. The use of optical Cherenkov detection remained, but the target medium was swapped from water to Antarctic Ice. Initially dust layers, bubbles and impurities in the ice meant that the produced Cherenkov photons were scattered too far for any useful reconstruction to be possible [24]. However, this effect was minimised by burying the detectors much deeper, where the ice layer was much more uniform; between two and three kilometres deep, after which prospects improved significantly. Today, AMANDA can be viewed as the prototype for the IceCube Neutrino Observatory¹⁰ [32]. IceCube constitutes the first kilometre volume neutrino telescope, completed over thirty years after the original DUMAND designs. Construction was fully completed in late 2010, and it has been observing continuously since then. It represents strong evidence towards the necessity of a detector of this size, as three years after construction was completed the collaboration reported the first detection of cosmic neutrinos [33], demonstrating that despite the wide range of challenges to overcome, it is indeed possible to detect HE neutrinos.

2.2.2 Status Today

Evidence for the cosmic neutrino flux has only increased since this initial detection, and it has been found to be largely isotropic, implying an extragalactic origin. Furthermore, other recent detections from IceCube include a transient source in the direction of TXS 0506+056, likely an extragalactic blazar, [34, 35], the steady point source starburst galaxy NGC 1068 [36] and in 2023, the collaboration released the first evidence of a diffuse neutrino flux originating from the galactic plane [37]. A large part of the recent influx of HE detections is indeed a product of the greater effective area of IceCube. However, it also draws upon

⁵Baikal Deep Underwater Neutrino Telescope

⁶Neutrino Mediterranean Observatory

⁷Neutrino Extended Submarine Telescope with Oceanographic Research Project

⁸Astronomy with a Neutrino Telescope and Abyss Environmental Research

⁹Antarctic Muon and Neutrino Detection Array

¹⁰IceCube.

the many years of preceding experiments; meaning that analysis and reconstruction techniques can be built upon and incrementally improved, allowing a thorough understanding of background and systematic uncertainties in these detectors to be generated. Ultimately, IceCube has successfully shown that there is significant cosmic neutrino flux to be detected on Earth, and that the building of large-scale telescopes needed to detect them is feasible and necessary. Now, more data is needed - more neutrino events to build sizable databases, and access to higher energy events.

IceCube will soon be joined by an array of kilometre-volume telescopes. Baikal-GVD¹¹, successor to the Baikal NT-200, and KM3NeT¹², successor to ANTARES, are both large-scale telescopes currently under construction, with early results released [38, 39]. The P-ONE¹³ telescope is currently in development, aiming to instrument the ocean off the coast of Vancouver, and has recently been joined by the TRIDENT¹⁴ experiment, in the west Pacific [40, 41]. Furthermore, IceCube itself is in the development stages of an upgrade, aiming to expand to \sim eight cubic kilometres as IceCube Gen2 - optical [42]. This next generation of telescopes will provide comprehensive sky coverage for cosmic neutrinos at TeV - PeV, leading to significant increases in neutrino event numbers in this energy range.

The current IceCube sensitivity range exhibits a cut-off at higher energies, above PeV energies. This is partly a continued consequence of the neutrino flux rates, which continue to rapidly decrease at higher energies, demonstrated in Fig. 2.2; in spite of the higher cross-sections of the particles at larger energies, causing the Earth to become increasingly opaque. Furthermore, neutrinos at or above these energies are of particular interest, as detailed earlier, for the identification of the UHECR sources and acceleration mechanisms. Therefore, this provides motivation to move to even higher values, expanding the neutrino energy range, which necessitates the development of new detection techniques and experiments.

There are a range of experiments focusing again on detecting neutrinos in ice, but searching for a different type of emission; radio-band Cherenkov emission. A high energy particle interacting in a dense medium such as ice produces a secondary cascade of relativistic particles, and the development of this cascade leads to the production of a coherent pulse of radio emission. The dominant mechanism behind the radio emission is the Askaryan effect, originally suggested by Askaryan in the 1960s [43, 44]. As the in-ice cascade develops, a net charge excess of electrons forms in the shower front, leaving behind a positively ionised cloud of charge. The charge excess is primarily caused by low energy scattering processes (e.g Compton, Bhabha, Møller) as well as positron annihilation [45], and it leads to coherent radio emission - produced according to Cherenkov effects as a cone at the Cherenkov angle from the shower axis. Detecting this radio pulse allows for the progenitor UHE neutrinos that produced the cascade to be identified.

The first forays into utilising Askaryan emission for this purpose began in the early 2000s

¹¹Baikal - Giga Volume Detector

¹² km^3 Neutrino Telescope

¹³Pacific Ocean Neutrino Experiment

¹⁴TRopIcal DEep-sea Neutrino Telescope

with experiments including the RICE¹⁵ and ANITA¹⁶ detectors [46, 47]. While Askaryan emission has successfully been detected in a number of accelerator experiments using sand [48], rock salt [49] and ice [47], it has not yet been detected from a neutrino cascade in location. It may be a matter of time however; current and future detectors utilising this detection method today include ARA¹⁷, ARIANNA¹⁸ and RNO-G¹⁹ [50–52], some of which are also serving as exploratory experiments for the radio component of the IceCube upgrade, IceCube Gen2-Radio [42]. The use of radio waves means that signals will travel far before dissipating, allowing for a more sparse instrumentation and subsequently greater cost-effective detection volumes, allowing them to aim for good sensitivity for neutrinos at energies $>EeV$, right at the end of the neutrino spectrum graph from where we can search for cosmogenic neutrinos.

This leaves a gap in the neutrino fluxes between PeV and EeV energies, from the highest IceCube sensitivities to the best of Askaryan experiment sensitivities, and this is the region that the Radar Echo Telescope for Neutrinos (RET-N) is aiming to fill.

2.2.3 RET-N

RET-N will aim to search for neutrino events of Pev - EeV energies, via radar techniques. In design, it is similar to the in-ice Askaryan arrays, with radio antennas buried in polar ice, and is also searching for secondary in-ice cascades generated by UHE neutrinos. However, instead of looking for the emission produced by the cascades, RET plans to use radar to actively search for the cascades themselves; specifically, the ionised trail left behind in the wake of the relativistic particles. This is achieved by illuminating a volume of ice with radio waves from a transmitter, which will scatter off the trail and produce a detectable radar echo recorded with in-ice receivers.

¹⁵Radio Ice Cherenkov Experiment

¹⁶Antarctic Impulse Transient Antenna

¹⁷Askaryan Radio Array

¹⁸Antarctic Ross Ice shelf Antenna Neutrino Array

¹⁹Radio Neutrino Observatory - Greenland

Figure 2.3: The RET-N sensitivity to an all-flavour diffuse neutrino flux (bold dashed red line), determined using 10 stations each running with 100kW of power, arranged similarly to the preliminary setup described in Fig. 2.4, 1.5km deep. Dashed lines represent experiment sensitivities while solid lines represent experimental upper-limits. Originally produced for [6], and modified to emphasise RET-N in [53]

A sensitivity study was performed for RET-N with ten years of observing time, and this is shown in Fig. 2.3, overlaid with a selection of other operating and proposed telescopes in similar energy ranges. The radar echo method will help fill the flux gap up to the Askaryan radio detectors, and has an easily scalable design which leads to the potential to provide a complementary detection technique for higher energies, producing increased statistics on the neutrino flux. Additionally, the radar method offers some specific benefits; the radar system allows for significant control over the expected reflection, which is largely dependent on the values of the transmitter frequency and signal power as set by the experiment [53]. Increased sensitivities can theoretically be reached by increasing the transmitted signal power, as long as this power can feasibly be produced. Furthermore, the radar reflection will emit over a much wider angular distribution - compared to direct Askaryan emission, which is limited to a specific angle - allowing for an increased detection horizon [54]. This, combined with well-established radar tracking techniques and multiple receivers ensures good potential for a variety of reconstruction methods with which to successfully identify and reconstruct UHE neutrinos.

Figure 2.4: A preliminary RET-N layout. A central transmitter (in red) is surrounded by receivers (black), all suspended on strings into the ice. Retrieved from [54].

An example antenna layout of RET-N is shown in Fig. 2.4, where a number of receiver strings are deployed into deep ice (1.5km) positioned around a central transmitter string [54]. Antennas will be positioned at large depths for several reasons: to lower experimental radio backgrounds, such as those found from galactic and anthropogenic sources; to increase the effective volume of the telescope, since the ice surrounding the antennas will also act as target material for the detector, to a certain extent; and to reduce the effects of impurities in ice that hinder the signal propagation [53, 55]. The refractive index of ice appears increasingly uniform at larger depths, reducing diffraction or refraction effects such as shadow zones, as reported in ice radio Cherenkov experiments [56, 57].

In summary, building upon the recent detections of the IceCube detector, the next goals for neutrino astronomy are largely focused on obtaining more data at a wider range of energies. This is where RET-N aims to contribute, using a novel detection technique to search for UHE neutrinos. As such, it will be part of a larger field of next generation telescopes searching for cosmic neutrinos. This includes the in-ice radio arrays described above but also a host of other experiments with different detection methods: air shower observatories such as the AugerPrime upgrade and GRAND²⁰ [58, 59] to the space-based experiments EUSO-SPB2²¹ and POEMMA²² [60, 61], to experiments aimed at specific neutrino flavours (ν_τ) including Trinity and TAMBO²³ [62, 63]. Many of these experiments have overarching UHE astroparticle detection capabilities, which include neutrinos among other messengers.

The current timeline of RET-N aims for deployment towards the latter half of the decade, joining many of these experiments. However, there is a lot to establish before this point, starting with validating the radar echo technique in-location. Furthermore, detecting the

²⁰Giant Radio Array for Neutrino Detection

²¹Extreme Universe Space Observatory on a Super Pressure Balloon II

²²Probe of Extreme Multi-Messenger Astrophysics

²³Tau Air-shower Mountain Based Observatory

signals will require the telescope to be self-triggered and the infrastructure of these triggers, effectiveness and combination with reconstruction methods requires testing and development. These requirements are being explored with the Radar Echo Telescope for Cosmic Rays (RET-CR).

Chapter 3

Radar and Air Showers

3.1 Radar Detection of Particle Cascades

While the ultimate goal of the RET collaboration is to look for UHE neutrinos with radar, the current form of the telescope (RET-CR) searches for the in-ice secondary cascades generated by cosmic ray (CR) air showers. This allows for the radar echo method to be tested in-situ with a target that is comparatively better understood. CR air showers can be detected both above the surface through their radio and particle emission, and below the surface with radar techniques. Reconstruction of the detected CR air showers performed with the radar measurements can then be validated with independent reconstruction from the surface systems, demonstrating the radar echo method.

3.1.1 Air Showers

A CR interacting in the atmosphere produces a cascade of particles. The cascade is often referred to as an extensive air shower (EAS) and is made up of hadronic, muonic and electromagnetic contributions [8]. As different components develop, they rapidly interact and decay, producing a distinctive development profile which can be well-described by a combination of cascade equations and numerical simulations. An EAS also produces a wide range of emission as it propagates through the atmosphere, allowing for multiple different detection mechanisms which have been utilised by a range of experiments; particle detector arrays, fluorescence telescopes, underground muon detectors, atmospheric Cherenkov telescopes and radio antennas. However, exploration has also been undertaken towards the detection of CR air showers with radar - specifically looking for the cascade in air, instead of in-ice as RET-CR does. These efforts have so far been unsuccessful, but the reasons behind this provide a clear illustration of the considerations required for the radar detection mechanism to work for in-ice both cosmic rays and neutrinos.

As an EAS propagates, it also leaves a short-lived trail of ionisation in its wake. Similarly to the neutrino in-ice cascades, if the trail has a high enough density - which depends on a number of factors - it is possible for it to scatter incident radio waves, producing a reflected pulse of radio waves, or radar echo. This is the mechanism behind the radar detection of air showers, and early experiments using this method were performed by Lovell and Blackett in 1941 [64] in Jodrell Bank, Manchester. Reports had been made of sporadic radio reflections ("reflexions") originating from low altitudes [65], and the two authors hy-

pothesised that this was the result of the cosmic ray ionisation trails described above, which they then set out to detect. Measurements of radar echoes were made successfully, but it became clear that these measurements, and the sporadic reflections, were very likely the result of meteor showers [66], and air showers remained elusive to radar. This was primarily due to an underestimated collisional damping effect from elastic collisions, which strongly suppressed the echo signal¹. Efforts were made to circumvent this effect with use of a higher gain antenna, aiming to increase the power of the scattered signal, but they proved unsuccessful and experiments were largely halted.

Discussion of the topic continued intermittently (e.g [68, 69]) until it was more strongly revived with the work of Gorham in 2001 [70] - a thorough review with updated calculations for the theoretical mechanisms behind the scatter, which led to renewed interest in the radar detection mechanism specifically for in-air showers from high energy cosmic rays and neutrinos. There was a need to find a cost-efficient way to instrument large areas of land in order to detect the higher energy ranges of the CR flux, and it was thought that this could be met with a radar-based array [71]. Furthermore, in comparison to fluorescence detectors utilised by UHECR arrays, a radar system would not require dark, moonless nights, leading to a much higher duty cycle. Further experimental work followed (e.g the Jicamarca [72] and MARIACHI [73] experiments), with the latter culminating in the TARA² experiment [74]. Unfortunately, the continued lack of detections from TARA [75], along with new theoretical considerations [76] strongly suggested that the technique would work only for select, very high energy showers ($\geq 10^{20}$ eV). The collisional damping effect identified previously, combined with the low ionisation densities found at the high altitudes of the showers meant that the ionisation trail was not dense enough to scatter, and led to the conclusion that all but the highest energy showers were undetectable via radar. This meant that building large scale efficient and cost-effective arrays with radar systems was determined to be unfeasible. However, RET-CR does detect CR air showers - on smaller scales - but only when they have generated secondary in-ice cascades. In fact, several characteristics of shower propagation in dense media lean favourably towards radar detection compared to in-air searches, allowing for both CRs and neutrinos to be detected.

3.1.2 In-Ice Particle Cascades

As a reminder, a particle cascade propagating through a dense medium again leaves behind free ionisation charges which produce a cloud of charge, or plasma³ and this represents the target of the radar systems. The issues encountered in air showers still remain; both the high collisional damping effects and the relatively short ionisation charge lifetimes, and the latter is important in determining the properties of the produced plasma [1]. However, these plasma properties are also determined by the ionisation density, which is related to the ionisation density of the medium. Since the densities found in ice are significantly higher than those in air, this means that the produced plasma is also much more dense. Furthermore, the lifetimes of the ionised electrons are related to both the temperature and purity of the

¹The damping effect was pointed out by a letter from a colleague at the time, but the letter was not found or read until years later. As it turned out, this missed correspondence is likely a key factor in the development of Jodrell Bank into the prolific radio observatory it became [67]

²Telescope Array RAdar

³The term plasma is used within to describe the ionisation trail, to stay consistent with other work e.g [77]. Whether this trail truly constitutes a plasma is discussed in [78].

medium, and increase at lower temperatures up to tens of nanoseconds around -60°C , as in deep ice. These two favourable factors reduce the suppression effects which plagued air shower plasma trails, and mean that the plasma found in-ice is capable of scattering incident radio waves at feasible detection frequencies for radar arrays. Whether this scatter can be achieved or not can be better described with the Radar Cross Section (σ_{RCS}), a property of the target that serves as a measure of the equivalent isotropic scattering area that the target presents as in a radar system [79]. The σ_{RCS} is dependent on the distances between the receiver, target and transmitter, as well as the gain and power of the transmitted signal, and a larger σ_{RCS} leads to a stronger echo signal from the radar system.

This possible detection method for high energy particle cascades was first raised and explored in salt [80] and in ice [81]. The possibility was further investigated with theoretical exploration and simulations [55, 82, 83], culminating in several SLAC laboratory experiments aimed at testing the scatter [84, 85]. The latter experiment successfully reported the detection of a radar echo signal. Here, high-density polyethylene was employed as the target material, in which a particle cascade was generated by an electron beam, chosen to mimic the properties of ice and neutrino showers. The target material was illuminated with a radio transmitter, and a receiver successfully recorded a radar echo pulse, scattered by the electron beam initiated cascade. With this result, the next step is to detect a radar echo from in-ice cascades in location, the current task of RET-CR.

Figure 3.1: Shown in (a) is the energy deposited into the ice from a Monte-Carlo simulated CR air shower, normal to the surface and produced by a 10^{17} eV proton. Here, a slice is taken through the centre of the in-ice shower. The estimated plasma frequency created by this in-ice energy deposit is shown in (b), produced using a form of Eq. 3.1. Both figures were retrieved from [86].

3.2 The RET-CR Test Beam

An EAS impacting an ice surface will transfer a portion of the energy it carries into the surface, producing an in-ice energy deposit with a profile of the kind shown in Fig. 3.1a. The amount of energy transferred to the ice correlates to the energy in the progenitor cascade at the time of impact. Keeping in mind the energy development of an air shower, it transpires that a collision close to the shower X_{max} will impart near the maximum amount of energy possible, which is desired for increased detection possibilities [1]. This point in the shower

development is dominated largely by photons, electrons and positrons, along with less significant muonic and hadronic contributions, and the different components are reflected in the shower footprint. This will extend to $\mathcal{O}(100\text{m})$ for the electromagnetic component, and $\mathcal{O}(\text{km})$ for the muonic component.

While the footprint can be very large, the secondary in-ice cascade is expected to appear differently, as a narrow beam of emission resembling in-ice neutrino cascades. This is partly due to the fact that the muonic and hadronic components are not expected to play significant roles in the shower propagation; the muonic component will simply pass through the ice sheet, while the hadronic contributes to the electromagnetic component via π_0 decay [86]. Instead, this latter electromagnetic component is more important in the development of the shower, and can be described in terms of the relevant critical particle energy ($E_c \approx 80$ MeV). Particles below this energy are dominated by ionisation losses, causing them disappear within a few radiation lengths (30 - 60cm for the top layers of ice), while particles with $E > E_c$ continue to propagate while experiencing pair-production and Bremsstrahlung processes. Within the shower profile shown in Fig. 3.1a, for a 10^{17} eV proton-initiated shower, particles with $E > E_c$ are produced only within $\mathcal{O}(10\text{cm})$ of the shower axis. This means that the in-ice cascade propagation is dominated by the HE particles in $\mathcal{O}(100\text{cm})$ of the shower core, producing a cascade geometry closely resembling the trail of a HE neutrino in-ice cascade that will be searched for by RET-N, allowing it to be used as a test beam for RET-CR. As it turns out, the main difference between the two cascades is the depths that they will be detected in, since CR air shower cascades are limited by the ice surface.

The appearance and production of the test beam has been established, but how effective is it as a scattering object for radio waves? To explore this, the plasma frequency ω_p can be introduced, a measurement of the ionisation density deposit that is dependent on the ionisation number density n_e , charge q and electron mass m , as in [1].

$$\omega_p = \sqrt{4n_e q^2 / m} \quad (3.1)$$

In a dense medium such as ice, ω_p is significantly higher than the density of ionisation in air, which increases the detection potential via radar. ω_p can be combined with the ionisation energy deposit with Fig. 3.1 to provide an estimate of the reflecting capabilities of the plasma. This is plotted in Fig. 3.1b using the energy deposit of Fig. 3.1a, where the colour scale now denotes $f_p = \omega_p / 2\pi$. This shows a narrow core of high frequencies (> 100 MHz), clearly resembling the energy deposit producing it. Efficient reflection occurs when the frequency of the incident radiation f_{TX} is lower than the plasma frequency f_p , which is feasible around this high frequency core. This then demonstrates that the secondary in-ice cascades from EAS are expected to produce radar echo signals in experimental conditions.

Figure 3.2: In (a) the frequency of the plasma produced by vertical air showers is shown, for a selection of CR progenitor energies, demonstrating the air-ice boundary over which f_p sharply increases for the more dense ice. A vertical line is placed at 100 MHz, the frequency below which detection with radar becomes more challenging. In (b), the number of deposited particles normalised by the maximum numbers are shown, for different CR progenitor energies, at both a high and low altitude. Both figures were retrieved from [1]

RET-CR looks for CR air showers with initial progenitor energies of approximately PeV - EeV, in order to meet certain constraints. The lower bound is a factor of the radar method; for the produced ionisation trail to scatter efficiently, the plasma frequency of the trail must be above a certain threshold, around 100 MHz. This translates into an energy threshold for the progenitor CR air shower, as the energy of the shower determines the energy of the secondary cascade and therefore the plasma frequency. For a range of progenitor energies, the expected plasma frequency in air and in ice are shown in Fig. 3.2a, where the difference between the air and ice plasma frequencies are clearly demonstrated, with the lowest energy air shower that still crosses the plasma threshold found around 10PeV. This limits the potential detection pool, as the CR flux also decreases for larger energies. But this can be mitigated by placing the experiment at high altitudes (> 2 km), increasing the probability that a particular EAS will impact the surface when it carries the maximum possible energy, near X_{max} . This is demonstrated in Fig. 3.2b, for air showers impacting at altitudes of 0 and 2.4km respectively (sea level and Antarctic ice sheet altitudes). This is especially important because the energy deposits are also dependent on arrival direction; above 30° inclinations, the transferred energy drops dramatically as a result of the larger EAS footprint spread. This is demonstrated in Fig. 3.3. Therefore, the PeV - EeV⁴ energy ranges maximise the deposited energy at the high altitudes, increasing radar detection potential for showers ranging from normal to 50° inclinations.

⁴The EeV upper limit is largely due to the CR flux decrease and the different triggering thresholds required for higher energies.

Figure 3.3: The energy (E_c) deposited into the ice within a 100cm radius of the shower axis at an altitude of 2.4km. Each point represents the average of 10 air showers at a particular zenith angle, and the energies are plotted as a function of the energy of the primary proton (E_p) that produced them, with E_c/E_p . Retrieved from [86].

3.3 The RET-CR Deployment

A planned layout of the components of RET-CR is shown in Fig. 3.4. The surface component consists of a number of surface stations, with each station equipped with methods to detect two forms of this emission; a pair of scintillators, for the cascade particles, a radio antenna to record the radio emission and a data acquisition (DAQ) system. Particle detectors are a well-established detection mechanism for air showers, and the scintillators in RET-CR (provided by the IceCube experiment, from the IceTop array [87]) are largely responsible for triggering the radar system. The system can be adjusted to only trigger on events above certain energies, around 10^{16} eV. On top of the energy constraints described earlier, energies below this threshold will become more challenging to reconstruct, and create rates of data too high to efficiently manage with the employed systems. The second detection mechanism via radio antennas are a more recent development, with extensive experimental efforts undergone in the last thirty years culminating in the building of large scale radio arrays searching for high energy air showers, including the Telescope Array [88] and the Pierre Auger observatory [58]. In RET-CR, the antennas used are log-periodic dipole arrays operating in the 50-350 MHz range [89], conceived from early SKA antenna designs [90]. Their role is to measure the radio emission produced by EAS in-air, allowing for both the trajectory and energy of the shower above the surface to be independently reconstructed.

Figure 3.4: The planned RET-CR deployment, as of 2022. The surface stations are marked with squares, each with a pair of cosmic ray detectors, and the in-ice antennas marked with circles, with the transmitter situated at the origin. Retrieved from [54].

The in-ice components host the radio antennas required for the radar system. A basic radar system involves a transmitter, receiver and signal processor [79]. The transmitter generates radio waves which propagate outwards until a suitable target appears in their path. The target absorbs and re-emits the radiation - the reflection, or scatter process - producing a radio echo that is detected by the receiver, and recorded by the signal processor. A distinction is generally made between a receiver and transmitter that are co-located (monostatic) and separated by some distance (bistatic) [91]. A majority of radar systems are monostatic, since bistatic operation introduces a fair amount of complexity for little operational benefit. However, there are particular applications to which bistatic, or multistatic (multiple receivers) systems are uniquely suited towards. In RET-CR, the radar system consists of a central RF transmitter surrounded by receivers, positioned in boreholes drilled into the ice surface. Multistatic radar is used, since it allows for increased target detection probability, effective instrumented volume, and greater flexibility in potential reconstruction methods. The transmitter is a vertical phased array transmitter made up of 8 total antennas, illuminating a range of depths approximately 2 - 20 m. It produces RF emission in the 150-300 MHz frequency range, which will be recorded by the surrounding receivers. The receivers detect the direct transmitter signal as a consequence of the bistatic design, which is not a desired signal and can over-saturate the systems. This is handled by a carrier-cancellation system implemented in the receivers, which effectively erases the transmitter signal from the system before amplification takes place [1]. The receivers are distributed approximately 30m from the transmitter, at depths of 10-13m, and consist of vertical dipole antennas. The antenna designs are based off of Askaryan in-ice radio experiments; ARA and ARIANNA [50].

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.5: A selection of antennas used in RET-CR. Image (a) is a picture of a surface station of RET-CR, from 2024, with the radio antenna and particle detector both visible. Picture taken by Simon De Kockere. Image (b) shows the antennas that make up the in-ice component of RET-CR, from the first deployment in 2023. Picture taken by Dylan Frikken.

Other equipment required to operate the experiment includes a solar array positioned centrally above the transmitter with batteries for poor weather conditions, as well as a DAQ, calibration and communication systems. During operation, the health and output of the experiment is monitored in real-time, through a wireless connection to a nearby station. Data analysis and reconstruction is currently performed offline, after the run is completed.

Figure 3.6: The RET-CR deployment of 2023, now with three in-ice receivers and three surface stations. The arrow towards Summit refers to the Greenland Summit Station. Retrieved from [92].

RET-CR was first deployed near Summit Station, Greenland, in the summer of 2023 (May to late August). The final deployment layout is shown in Fig. 3.6, consisting of three receivers

and three surface stations [92]. The experiment operated successfully for approximately 9 days, but encountered issues thanks to overheating in the DAQ systems. A new heat sink design has consequently been tested and implemented in the second deployment, which began operating in late May 2024 and is scheduled to take data until mid August. The system is now situated above the ice, and the entire structure consists of four receivers and five surface stations, which have been taking data for a good few weeks, at time of writing.

Chapter 4

Methods

The appearance of the radar echo signal, as will hopefully soon be seen in the RET-CR experiment, depends on many factors including the transmitter frequency, detector geometry, ice properties and radar systems. This motivates the simulation-based study of the signals generated with this detection method, to ensure good understanding of the signal and the ways in that it might be utilised. Previous work including [93, 94] provides useful expectations for the types of effects expected to be found, such as significant direction-dependent properties, likely caused by different, overlapping mechanisms. In this work, the C++ code package **MARES** was used; the Macroscopic Approach to the Radar Echo Scatter. This provides a different method with which to investigate signal properties, and has allowed for the results within to be produced. The following chapter details the methods used to undergo this study, beginning with the simulation setup and necessary radar descriptions, before introducing the experimental approach and analysis methods used, which will then be applied in the following chapter.

4.1 MARES

MARES is a semi-analytical code, designed to simulate the radar signal received from scattering off the plasma produced by relativistic cascades. Much of the following section is summarised from [77], and a full description of the code can be found in [78]. An event in **MARES** begins with the generation of the particle cascade, using established parameterisations commonly applied to air showers (Greisen, Nishimura and Kamata) in order to define the longitudinal and lateral shower profiles. These parameterisations are modified for ice propagation by adjusting the critical energy, Molière radius and interaction lengths - although these variables can be adjusted for different media, such as high density polyethylene. This is combined with a mean ionisation energy in order to produce a density profile of the free ionised charge density created by the cascade, which has already been linked to the respective plasma frequency and scattering strength. At this point, the cascade is split into semi-circular segments. The volume of these segments can be adjusted, but need to be kept small enough for coherence within the model to be retained, with length scales much lower than the transmitter signal wavelength. Combined with transparency, plasma lifetime and attenuation factors, the magnitude of the final signal is then found as a sum of the scattered fields produced by each segment, using transmitter and receiver antennas positioned by the user within the chosen medium.

The use of cascade parameterisations means that the code is deterministic, producing the same results for the same inputs. This is in contrast to Monte-Carlo based codes, such as `RadioScatter` [55], an alternative method for simulating radar echo signals. `RadioScatter` takes external input for the in-ice cascade (e.g Monte-Carlo cascades generated in-ice with the GEANT4 toolkit [95]), and then calculates the expected electric field for the ionisation deposit produced by the inputted cascade, tracking each individual contributing charge. This allows it to represent event-to-event fluctuations that are not captured in `MARES`, because of the macroscopic view. However, this view does mean that `MARES` events can be generated very quickly - producing an event takes $\mathcal{O}(10)$ seconds, which is very useful for exploring a wide range of input parameters that could affect the subsequent signal. The current antenna parameters are set so that the transmitter uses a Hertzian dipole radiation pattern, and the receiver an isotropic antenna model. The effective area and antenna length are adjusted by a maximum gain parameter, leaving the gain pattern constant. `MARES` has no definition of a surface, only a surrounding volume - in this work, surface refers to the plane from which cascades are set to originate from, resembling their production from EAS in RET-CR. Furthermore, the whole volume is instantaneously illuminated with radio waves from the transmitter; zero-time in the produced signal signifies the time at which the cascade is generated. Finally, in its current form `MARES` uses a constant index of refraction of $n = 1.78$, but the code includes the capability to use a more realistic ice model, which will likely be addressed in future analyses.

Figure 4.1: In (a), a diagram of the coordinate system used within is shown. The transmitter and receiver locations are fixed and referenced in cartesian coordinates, as in Fig. 4.2. The track of a cascade is shown in orange, with the initial cascade position also defined in cartesian coordinates as in Fig. 4.1a, and the arrival direction via a zenith angle θ and azimuth angle ϕ . A zenith of $\theta = 0^\circ$ is collinear with the z axis, and an azimuth of $\phi = 0^\circ$ to the x axis, increasing clockwise towards the y axis. In (b), the depth of the antennas is highlighted, each positioned 10m into the ice.

4.2 Approach

In order to investigate signal properties, a range of signals will be generated using MARES which will then be explored in light of any particular features or trends that may be of interest; for later reconstruction purposes, or to improve understanding of signatures of the echo signal. For any specific property, the aim is to be able to explain the process causing it or predict how it changes with certain simulation parameters. These findings can then be evaluated on a larger scale for RET-CR, and for their utility in reconstruction methods.

Figure 4.2: Simulation antenna positions, for three receivers (left) and one receiver (right). The transmitter is marked with a dark blue triangle, and receivers with light green inverted triangles. Both antennas are positioned 10m below the plane where the cascades originate (Fig. 4.1b).

4.2.1 Simulation Detector setup

Keeping this in mind, the results presented within are chosen to resemble where possible the RET-CR deployment and experimental parameters. This naturally excludes a region of possible signals (e.g upward-going cascades in the detector) that are not produced by the target trails left by CR air showers. Nevertheless, this setup improves applicability to RET-CR, allowing for any identified effects to be extended to RET-CR signals later. It also provides a useful starting point in the investigation, when there are many possible simulation parameters to be adjusted. If any particularly interesting signatures are identified, the phase space can then be expanded later as necessary. The possible simulation parameters can be split into categories:

- **Cascade parameters:** arrival direction, energy, position.
- **Detector parameters:** transmitter frequency, power, gain, antenna depth, polarisation.

- **MARES parameters:** sampling ratio, cascade segment size, refractive index, plasma lifetime.

The antenna positions used within are marked in Fig. 4.2. The detector setup in which events were simulated was chosen largely to resemble RET-CR, with similar energies and length scales. The setup in Fig. 3.4 employs three (or more) receivers, which can be translated to the layout in Fig. 4.2 using the coordinate systems shown in Fig. 4.1a. The angle between the transmitter, receiver and target is known as the bistatic angle β , shown in Fig. 4.3b. Velocities can be introduced into the description by the use of the aspect angle δ , subtended between the bisector of the bistatic angle and the velocity vector of the target, also see Fig. 4.3b. The bistatic and aspect angles are generally used to describe movement in a bistatic radar setup, with the latter becoming more important when discussing Doppler effects. On top of this, two other angles can be defined: RVP and TVP, describing the angle between the target velocity vector and the receiver or transmitter respectively, shown in Fig. 4.3a.

Figure 4.3: In (a), the TVP and RVP angles are defined. In (b), the bistatic and aspect angles are shown. In both plots, the transmitter - target and receiver - target distances are marked, with R_R and R_T . The distance between the two antennas is also emphasised, and normally referred to as the antenna baseline.

A MARES event includes a receiver, transmitter and cascade; creating an event with three receivers involves running the code three times with the receiver in three different locations. In practice, this means that generating an event for all three receivers rarely offers new insight for investigating signal properties. Therefore, the majority of the properties investigated within are between a single transmitter and receiver pair as shown in Fig. 4.1b. The use of multiple receivers becomes more important for both overall trends of possible signals, and reconstruction techniques such as interferometry, which will be explored in later sections.

In order to investigate properties in this setup, two approaches were taken using the possible parameters: 1. Varying cascade parameters in order to simulate the possible signal

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Value</i>
Antenna Gain	15 dBi
TX Power	50 W
Polarisation	z (Vertical)
Antenna Depth	10m
Sampling ratio	100
Segment Radius	0.1 mm
Segment Length	0.1 cm
Plasma Lifetime	10 ns

Table 4.1: Default Detector and MARES parameters. Polarisation refers to the orientation of the antenna within the detector, and can be set to x, y and z; the effects of varied polarisation are demonstrated in Figures A.7 and A.8. Sampling ratio controls the rate at which the produced signal is sampled, and is shown as a ratio to reduce the possibility of a low sampling rate leading to incorrect representation of the signal. The segment radius and length control the volume of each cascade segment. The volumes must be small enough that coherence remains, and smaller volumes lead to longer runtimes for each event. Other parameters not defined here are explained in the following section.

population in RET-CR and 2. Investigating the effects of varying detector and MARES parameters on signal properties. The former is useful for improving the understanding of signals seen in the detector for the chosen parameters, and also for testing reconstruction methods. For this setup, default detector and MARES parameters were determined and used for most simulations, as seen in Table 4.1, with values obtained predominantly from [92, 96]. Meanwhile, varying these parameters for fixed cascades - as done in the second approach - allows for investigation into the sensitivity of different properties for the simulation and detector layouts. For example, the extent to which changing the depth of the antennas affects the produced signal amplitude. Once events were generated, the different properties could be compared with respect to the input parameters and the geometry of the events within the radar system, with bistatic angles, antenna ranges, expected Doppler shifts and arrival times. This was achieved by creating a Python code structure which simultaneously produced events to be generated with MARES, and calculated the respective radar quantities for each event.

Figure 4.4: In (a), the position of the signal shown in 4.5. The arrival direction is chosen for a vertical cascade $(180,0)^\circ$. In (b), the three-dimensional view of this event is shown.

Figure 4.5: An example radar echo signal as seen in the receiver, with the position and arrival direction shown in Fig. 4.4b, energy of 20PeV and other parameters of Table 4.1. The generated signal is purely the result of the cascade scatter; no noise is included in the signal.

4.2.2 Signal Properties

This section details the investigated signal properties and main analysis methods used for each property, employing the example signal shown in Fig. 4.5, produced for a vertical cascade positioned at (15,20)m within the detector setup (4.4b).

Peak Amplitude

A measurement of the strength of the signal can be obtained using the peak amplitude. This is simply the largest absolute value obtained by the signal over the duration. Each peak amplitude will be therefore by retrieved for a particular point in the signal duration,

the peak amplitude time.

Power

An alternative measurement of signal strength is the power of the signal, obtained by first applying a Hilbert transform [97] to the waveform and then integrating the transform over time. This measure is more stable against sharp peak fluctuations than the peak amplitude, but tends to provide smaller values for short duration signals than long duration.

Arrival Time

For the signal property analysis, this is defined as the very first non-zero value of the signal. In reality, this would be an unachievable measurement due to signal noise; arrival times for more realistic signals will be discussed later. This definition is used mainly to improve intuition over the signal when discussing properties. Furthermore, by also retrieving the last non-zero waveform value the effective duration of the signal, or pulse width, can be retrieved.

Figure 4.6: The waveform in Fig. 4.5, converted to the frequency domain. The vertical grey line is placed at 0.25 GHz, the transmitter frequency used in the event, which corresponds to the strongest frequency response. The transmitter frequency remains a strong contribution in most signals, but is occasionally superseded by other effects.

Peak Frequency

The frequency content of the time-domain signal can also be explored. This is done using a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) algorithm, the results of can be seen in Fig. 4.6. With this transform, the peak frequency value can be obtained by retrieving the frequency at which the the signal is strongest. In this case, this is around the transmitter frequency (0.25 GHz) marked in grey. Furthermore, the frequency was also investigated through the use of a spectrogram, shown in Fig, 4.7, along with the waveform and FFT. Unlike the FFT, a spectrogram provides timing information on the frequency content, leading to a clearer picture of the frequency domain. However, retrieving a peak frequency value from a spectrogram presents a challenge, and for speed and ease of application this value was retrieved from the FFT for analysis, and where needed compared against the signal spectrogram for validation.

In practice, an FFT is a relatively simple, well established method for time-frequency analysis, which nonetheless requires some care to use correctly. For example, a Fourier transform assumes by nature that the inputted signal is periodic. Therefore, applying a transform to a signal which is not can produce spurious frequency content known as spectral leakage,

possibly superseding the true frequency values in the signal. It isn't possible to completely avoid this effect, but it can be reduced by applying a window transform to the signal before using the FFT. There are several types of windows optimised for different uses, but generally the goal is to ensure that the start and end points of the signal are both zero, effectively transforming the signal to a periodic one. However, a window transform was not applied to the MARES signals within, as both sides of the signal are already padded with zeroes as part of the simulation procedure. Applying a window to this signal then only reduces the strength of the subsequent FFT; in fact, applying a window to a periodic signal can actually cause spectral leakage.

On the other hand, a spectrogram consists of multiple short-length FFTs taken over the whole signal, akin to a sliding window view of the frequency of the signal. Using this method means that a choice has to be made between high time resolution and high frequency resolution, as it isn't possible to have both. In this work, an attempt has been made to account for this effect, with the method described in [98]. This involves creating two spectrograms of each signal, with a very long window length and a very short window length respectively, corresponding to high frequency resolution and high time resolution. The two spectrograms are then multiplied in order to obtain a combination of both, where the only frequency responses that survive are those that are present in both spectrograms. This reduces the leakage effect and allows for better time information to be retrieved from the spectrogram. The downsides of this method are that it can introduce some striped artefacts into the final spectrogram, and it takes a significant amount of time to produce, from ~ 30 seconds to two minutes in some cases, which makes the analysis of large numbers of events unfeasible without more computationally efficient methods.

Figure 4.7: Generated waveform example, now shown in white and overlaid on top of a spectrogram. The FFT of the entire signal is shown to the left of the spectrogram, and orientated to align the frequency axis of the two.

Figure 4.8: The profile of an event cascade, produced with the density of ionised electrons (N_e) produced by the cascade. This can be compared to the ionised energy deposit simulated in Fig. 3.1a.

Cascade Profile

A typical cascade profile, created using the produced density of ionised electrons in the medium is shown in Fig. 4.8. This describes the development of the cascade through the ice, where the number of ionised particles presents as a narrow column increasing in density up to a peak, before gradually dissipating. It is useful to investigate, because the ionised electron number correlates to the σ_{RCS} calculation performed by MARES. Specifically, the σ_{RCS} is calculated for each segment with Eq. 4.1, where $\sigma_{sc,i}$ is the segment RCS for a particular segment i , and σ_e is the RCS for a single electron.

$$\sigma_{sc,i} = N_{e,i}^2 \sigma_e \quad (4.1)$$

The time-dependent $\sigma_{sc,i}(t)$ is then found using Eq. 4.2, where the plasma lifetime τ and initial production time t_0 are now included [77].

$$\sigma_{sc,i}(t) = \sigma_{sc,i} e^{-t/\tau} \Theta(t - t_0) \quad (4.2)$$

Since σ_{RCS} is related to the power of the expected radar scatter, we can use this profile to obtain an estimate of the strength of the signal returned from each region of the scattering plasma. MARES uses parameterised cascades, which means that this density distribution is identical for each event with the same initial energy. However, the appearance of the distribution in the frame of the receiver depends on both the arrival direction and position of the event.

In the left of Fig. 4.9, in dashed orange lines, the same profile is shown but now the ionised electrons in each radial segment are summed and plotted against the receiver length. The receiver length is not the length of the cascade, which would also be identical for each event, but the length of the cascade as it appears to the receiver. An event with a different position and arrival direction may then have a shorter receiver length, even though the cascade length does not change. Furthermore, the location of the strongest reflecting region of the cascade, currently found around five to ten metres for the example event, may also change with a different cascade trajectory.

Cascade Phase

This quantity describes the total phase of the scattered field as seen in the receiver, made

up of individual contributions from each segment volume signal, and shown in Fig. 4.9. In MARES, the phase array of a cascade is 'switched on' by the propagating cascade. The duration for which it then remains, seen in the width of the striped rectangle, is controlled by the plasma lifetime τ . The colour of the plot at a receiver length then specifies the phase received from the segment over the time the plasma remains in the ice. The changing phase has been produced here as a function of time over the entire event, but in the perspective of the receiver it can be sampled at particular times, which is shown in the left of the figure; the phase of the array at a specific (receiver) time. In Fig. 4.9, this is overlaid on the waveform and total phase with a grey line, and the respective phase at that time is shown to the left of the plot in blue. Here, it is plotted again over the receiver length, but the phase is shown on the x axis instead of on a colour scale.

Figure 4.9: The phase of the received signal over time. The top graph displays the specific waveform for the event, underneath which is shown the total phase of the cascade for the entire signal. The grey line overlaid over the two is chosen for a specific time, and the phase at this time is plotted on the left of the figure, against the length of the cascade in the frame of the receiver.

Antenna Gain and Transmitter Power

Both the antenna gain and transmitter power affect only the magnitude of the voltage waveform, shown in Figures 4.10 and 4.11. Both would play more of a role in the case of more realistic antenna patterns, but in the limits of this work, remain largely untouched, except to increase amplitude magnitudes in the case of a wide event generation.

Figure 4.10: Effects of varying antenna gain on generated signals. A varied gain value signifies that the inputted maximum gain of both the receiver and transmitter have been modified, and the two values are always kept equal.

Figure 4.11: Effects of varying transmitter power on generated signals. The receiver power is fixed to zero, since it is not generating any radiation.

Figure 4.12: Effects of different cascade energies on generated signals.

Cascade Energy

The cascade energy in MARES represents the energy held by the particle inducing the cascade. In RET-CR, cascades are not generated by single particles but by the impact of the high energy core of an air shower at the surface. This is approximated within the simulation by retrieving the energies transferred to the ice from air showers (Fig. 3.3 as generated in simulations in [86]). Increasing the initial cascade energy also increases the magnitudes of the respective waveforms 4.12. The higher energies produce more numerous particle cascades,

increasing the reflecting return power of the plasma which produces stronger signals. To a certain extent, higher initial energies also produce longer cascades, increasing the section of plasma capable of reflecting which does reflect on the geometry of the setup.

Figure 4.13: Generated signals for varied plasma lifetimes.

Plasma Lifetime

The plasma lifetime in MARES describes the ionised charge lifetime that helps determine plasma properties, as described earlier. If this value is lowered, the plasma will more short-lived, and it will be harder for it to scatter any radio waves. The effect of this is demonstrated in Fig. 4.13. For short lifetimes (1 ns), the signal strength is small and the duration is short. Up until ~ 50 ns, both these parameters are increased, but for lifetimes past this threshold the amplitude of the signal remains mostly stable, and the main effect is now seen in the increased duration of the signal. This is also explored in [99].

4.3 Mapping Methods

Figure 4.14: A vertical cascade, with a zenith angle of $\theta = 180^\circ$.

This section describes the mapping methods used within, for both position and arrival direction. In order to best illustrate this some results of these methods are shown, but the features seen will not be explored until the next chapter. The first step undertaken was to gain an overview of the signal amplitude for many different positions. This was achieved by generating cascade events at uniform positions across a coordinate square, normally centered around the TX or RX. Each signal has the same parameters and will head vertically down into the ice relative to the antennas - shown in Fig. 4.14. For a particular position, the respective signal as seen in the receiver can be analysed to retrieve the peak amplitude, and then plotted respective to the original event position. This results in a 2D plot describing the peak amplitude, akin to a map. An example of this can be seen in Fig. 4.15.

Figure 4.15: An example coordinate square of events for the position map method. Each orange dot represents a generated signal, from which the peak amplitude of the event is retrieved and plotted at that position. This produces the position-amplitude map plot shown on the right. Both the receiver and transmitter in this plot can be seen as a distinct black point, which is an artefact of the current MARES; at arrival directions where a cascade points directly into an antenna, the segmentation approximation breaks down and the produced signal is disrupted. This scenario occurs rarely in the following analysis, and is easily spotted in the signal.

This method is very effective in showing the relative changes in amplitude for position. By increasing the amount of events in a fixed coordinate square, the resolution of the produced plot can be increased. Since this scales as N^2 , care has to be taken not to produce very large numbers of events, but this method requires only the waveform and duration of each event, which take up very little space, meaning that high resolution plots can be achieved without occupying too much storage space ($\sim 200\text{Mb}$ for a map of 10,000 events). The other consideration is computing time; running thousands of events does quickly raise the time scale for jobs. On a cluster computing environment however this doesn't pose any real issue, especially if parallel jobs can be utilised.

Figure 4.16: In (a), the three-dimensional view of the varied arrival directions is shown. This translates to the two-dimensional view shown in (b), with a vertical cascade originating from the centre of the polar plot. Moving outwards from the centre corresponds to a steeper zenith angle, and moving clockwise from north corresponds to a changing azimuth angle.

Figure 4.17: A polar plot for a cascade fixed at a position of $(15,20)m$. The colour scale is kept at a low opacity, in order to emphasise the zenith and azimuth coordinates around the plot. Each orange marker signifies a produced signal at that arrival direction.

To gain an overview of varying arrival directions, a slightly different method is used. Parameters are kept constant, as for previous plots, but now a specific position is chosen for all cascades to originate from. The arrival direction of each cascade is then varied over a

fixed range of possible trajectories (Figures 4.16a and 4.16b) and the peak amplitude of each respective signal is then plotted according to the input arrival direction, generating a trajectory-amplitude polar plot as seen in Fig. 4.17. In this plot especially, a range of interesting effects are clearly apparent.

Both these position and arrival direction overviews generate forms of maps, which is useful because it allows for effective and relatively quick estimates of different signal properties, especially as large-scale overviews of the global properties. Once the events and signals have been generated, a variety of different properties (peak frequency, arrival times, power) can be plotted, since it is not confined to peak amplitude. It is also relatively unique to MARES, in that it makes use of the computationally efficient code. If events routinely required minutes or hours generate, the method would become much less feasible except for very low resolution maps.

Chapter 5

Signal Properties

An overview of the signal peak amplitudes is shown in Fig. 5.2, and similarly for peak frequencies in Fig. 5.3, where a selection of positions have been chosen from within the detector setup. At each position, arrival direction plots have been made, as described in Section 4.3. Positions are chosen only from one half of the total possible plane of origin, since events produced on either side of the transmitter-receiver baseline are symmetric, which means that the half of the plane not sampled will have an identical distribution inverted over the baseline. Considering all the individual polar plots of Fig. 5.2 and Fig. 5.3, it can be seen that there are several common features shared between them. In order to investigate these features, a particular polar plot will be selected, positioned at (15,20)m; Fig. 5.1. This position is not chosen for a significant reason beyond its equal distance from the antennas, and relative proximity to the baseline, but exploring the effects in this particular polar plot allows for the mechanisms behind the identified features to be discussed and then applied more generally to the wider signal properties.

Figure 5.1: Peak amplitude (left) and peak frequency (right) polar plots for a fixed position of $(15,20)m$. These are also shown in Figures 5.2 and 5.3. The arrival directions range from zenith angles of 180° to 130° , for all possible azimuth angles. The amplitude scale is set to the maximum and minimum values found within the plot, causing it to appear brighter than in Fig. 5.2. The frequency scale remains the same, with a line drawn to indicate the value of the transmitter frequency as is found in the centre band of the frequency plot.

Figure 5.2: Amplitude polar plots generated for a selection of possible positions in the detector geometry. The amplitude scale for each polar plot is fixed to demonstrate wider peak amplitude variations, and plots are scaled to be as large as possible, while still fitting alongside each other in the position plane. Accordingly, the position of each event for a particular plot is found at the centre of that plot.

Figure 5.3: Frequency polar plots generated for a selection of possible positions in the detector geometry. The frequency scale has been fixed for each plot.

The plots in Fig. 5.1 appear to demonstrate significant variations in amplitude and frequency according to their arrival directions. Distinct features within the plots include a curve of disrupted amplitudes and high frequencies situated on the left of each plot; a striped region of low amplitude and low or disrupted frequencies on the right, and a vertical band of high amplitude and constant (transmitter) frequency. To explore the signals producing these effects, a selection of them, marked in Fig. 5.4, are plotted in Fig. 5.5, for a zenith angle of 140° with both fixed and normalised waveforms. The normalised waveforms show the range of differences in these signals over possible azimuth angle, with noticeable variations in frequency and duration. In the fixed waveforms, both the signals at 0° and 180° , originating from the vertical band, have noticeably higher amplitudes - this will be explored in the following section.

Figure 5.4: The sampled events in Fig. 5.5, overlaid in grey markers to indicate their arrival directions.

Figure 5.5: A selection of individual waveforms from the (15,20)m polar plot. Waveforms are plotted both with a fixed scale (left) and individually normalised (right). The zenith angle for each plot is kept at 140° , with corresponding azimuth angles marked on each plot, as shown in Fig. 5.4. Plots at 0° and 180° originate from the vertical high amplitude band, while plots at 55° and 270° reflect the ring and striped features.

5.1 Plasma Coherence

5.1.1 Amplitude

In Fig. 5.2, it can be seen that polar plots positioned further away from the antennas generally exhibit lower amplitudes than those nearby, and a vertical cascade - found in the direct centre of each polar plot - will have close to the highest possible amplitude at that position. For steeper arrival directions, the amplitudes decrease significantly - with two exceptions. The first occurs at (15,0)m where high amplitudes can be found in the majority of the polar plot. This is because of the position of the plot on the baseline, which represents a particular region in the radar setup wherein signals are expected to present significantly differently. In general, the returned radar signal from targets or cascades on the baselines is both high and homogeneous, which improves the probability of detection but can present issues when searching for the position of the cascades, since every signal on the baseline appears similarly [91]. Since this only accounts for a small region of the detector setup, the investigation focused largely on positions beyond this region.

The second exception to the antenna proximity - amplitude correlation is found in the bands of high amplitude, found in nearly all polar plots. Clearly, for a certain position within the detector geometry, there exists a range of arrival directions for which the amplitude of the signal will be noticeably higher, which may point to some form of boosting effect occurring for events at favourable trajectories.

Figure 5.6: Waveforms, frequency content and phase plots for two events: Event A ($170, 270^\circ$), located outside of the boosted amplitude region and event B ($175, 90^\circ$), picked from inside the region. The arrival directions of both events are marked on the plots (left). The frequency spectra are shown in the middle, and the phase on the right, with the selected phase taken for both waveforms at the time of peak amplitude.

This can be investigated further by exploring individual signals. In Fig. 5.6 two events are shown from the (15,20)m polar plot. Event A is selected from outside the boosted region, ($170, 270^\circ$), while event B is chosen from securely within the boosted region at ($175, 90^\circ$). Accordingly, the waveform of event A is an order of magnitude lower in amplitude when compared to event B. Focusing for now on the phase of the events, it can also be seen that the phase of A at the peak amplitude time exhibits lots of oscillation. This suggests that the signal contributions from each segment of the cascade are out of phase with respect to each

other, and therefore the total signal produced by the segments is exhibiting decoherence at this particular time in the receiver. The phase of event B also shows some oscillation at the top of the receiver length, but it also exhibits a section in which the oscillation stops, no longer crossing the phase axis at 0.5π . This suggests that the contributions of each segment are now in phase, meaning that each individual segment signal in this region, and for this time, sum coherently. Therefore, it appears that whether the signal from each segment of the cascade arrives coherently, or not, has a significant effect on the strength of the measured signal.

A larger selection of events within the band are shown in Fig. 5.8, with corresponding arrival directions marked in Fig. 5.7. Each event also exhibits a region of coherence, leading to the conclusion that if, for a small amount of time, coherence is reached, this strongly increases the signal amplitude. For clarity, this mechanism will be referred to as plasma coherence from this point onwards.

Figure 5.7: . The sampled events shown in 5.8.

Figure 5.8: . Individual plots for four events in the coherence region: A $(140,0)^\circ$, B $(160,0)^\circ$; C $(160,180)^\circ$, D $(140,180)^\circ$. The locations of each event are also shown in Fig. 5.7. Each event has coherence at a region in the receiver length and a high amplitude between 8×10^{-7} and 2×10^{-6} . Events C and D have lower amplitudes due to their directions facing away from the receiver. This effect occurs consistently throughout all polar plots, and can be seen to disappear if the polarisation is adjusted, as in Fig. A.7.

It is possible to spot areas of coherence in the full phase plot, not just the time specific function; it occurs for any area in the plot where the stripes are orientated near or completely vertically. If a particular chosen time - represented with a grey line in each plot - is parallel at any point to stripes in the array, this region will be coherent. In the plots of Fig. 5.8, it becomes clear that coherence is not just reached at the peak amplitude times of each

event, but for other regions of the phase array. For example, event A in Fig. 5.8 exhibits coherence throughout the phase array, for the receiver lengths between 7.5 to 10m. However, the amplitude is only boosted near the front of the array, and not for later times. Also in Fig. 5.9, events B, C and D exhibit coherence, but from times later than the peak amplitude time of each signal. Therefore, there is another factor to be considered in order for this to occur, involving the profile of the cascade itself. As a reminder, this is represented in phase plots with dashed orange lines, showing the normalised cascade profile.

Figure 5.9: . Four events with different arrival directions. A, B and D are from outside of the coherence region, and their phases are shown for times later than the peak amplitude time. C is within the region, at peak amplitude time, shown for comparison.

In Fig. 5.9, it can be seen that even though phase coherence is reached at different times for each event, the coherence region is often far from the region of the cascade that provides the most reflecting power, and the signal at this time is not boosted. Whereas the coherence

and strongest profile regions in event C match very well, leading to a sizeable increase in the signal amplitude. Therefore, the conditions that must be met for this boosting effect to happen are that phase coherence in the plasma occurs, at a region that roughly correlates with the strongest part of the cascade.

If this coherence never occurs, there should be no boosting effect. This can be tested by reproducing the polar plot of Fig. 5.1, with a much shorter plasma lifetime ($\tau = 0.1\text{ns}$). The resulting low plasma lifetime signals are shown in Fig. 5.10, where it can be seen that the boosted region has now disappeared. It has been replaced by a relatively steady amplitude, leaving only the previously identified interference effects, which will also be explored later. Comparing individual signals from the low plasma lifetime in Fig. 5.11 and the default lifetime, it can be seen that in this region the segments are no longer in phase, despite their favourable geometry, because the plasma is now too short-lived for coherence between different plasma sections to occur.

Figure 5.10: . The effect of varying plasma lifetime (τ). The top row polar plots are produced with $\tau = 0.1\text{ ns}$, and the bottom row shows the reference polar plots, with $\tau = 10\text{ ns}$.

Figure 5.11: . Individual signals for varying plasma lifetime. Both waveforms are for $(175, 90)^\circ$; the top row is generated with $\tau = 10$ ns (default parameter) and the bottom with $\tau = 0.1$ ns.

Figure 5.12: . The effect of plasma lifetime on the frequency of events. Each column shows the an event at the same arrival direction and position - events A and B shown in Fig. 5.6, with the top row generated with $\tau = 0.1$ ns and the bottom with $\tau = 10$ ns.

In summary, the coherence of the plasma produced by a cascade can cause a boosting effect on the produced signal. For this to occur, the cascade has to be at a favourable arrival direction, where the strongest part of the cascade correlates with a region of coherence. Furthermore, this link between phase coherence and signal amplitude has been demonstrated quantitatively by the MSc student Jannes Loonen, who created a measure of the amount of coherence in each phase plot. When combined with the cascade profile, it was found to correlate very well to signal amplitudes over a range of possible cascade parameters, leading to reasonable confidence in this mechanism.

5.1.2 Frequency

Up until this point, the focus has been on the effect of plasma coherence on the signal amplitude, but it is clear that the plasma coherence region corresponds to a similar region in frequency space. Here, the peak frequency of each signal is found at the transmitter frequency, and there are distinct boundaries bordering the region, beyond which frequency shifts start to appear. Indeed, in the frequency spectra of Fig. 5.6, a sharp difference in the FFTs of the two events can be seen, with event B peaked at the transmit frequency, and event A demonstrating a broader response. Furthermore, if we look again at the low plasma lifetime example of Fig. 5.10, where the boosting effect has been removed, we see also that the distinct region disappears. In the individual signals of Fig. 5.12, the dominant transmitter frequency contribution has been removed for event B - outside of the coherence region - leading to the smoother frequency distribution in the $\tau = 0.1\text{ns}$ polar plot.

The similar appearances of this frequency region and the plasma coherence region leads to the conclusion that plasma coherence boosts both the signal amplitude and transmitter frequency response, leading to an identifiable region in both signal properties. However, comparing the polar plots in Figures 5.2 and 5.3 it can be seen that there are small differences in the extent of both regions, with the frequency feature generally wider than the amplitude feature. This is largely due to issues in defining the peak frequency value, instead of a true difference in the properties. Looking back to Fig. 5.6, the FFT of event A has a small peak at the transmitter frequency as well as a broad upshift. Visually, it can be seen that this event is no longer boosted by plasma coherence, and the larger contribution to the frequency is from the upshift. However, because the shift presents as less of a sharp peak than the transmitter frequency component, the peak frequency of this value is still returned as the transmitter frequency. To properly account for this, a more accurate description of the frequency content would need to be implemented. Accordingly, the two regions are both concluded to be produced by the plasma coherence mechanism.

Figure 5.13: The peak frequency of random signals, plotted according to bistatic angle β and aspect angle δ . Event positions are randomly sampled from a 200m by 200m square centered on the antennas, with zenith angles of 180° to 130° , for a fixed energy of 20PeV. The bistatic and aspect angle are calculated from the strongest point in the cascade profile, corresponding to a cascade length of $\sim 7.5m$.

However, there is another contributing factor to the frequency polar plots, from Doppler shifting of the signals. Doppler shifts are largely responsible for the peak frequency values outside of the plasma coherence region, and the extent of their influence can be explored with the Doppler equation for bistatic radar, Eq. 5.1. This consists of the sum of the projections of the target velocity onto the transmitter and receiver line-of-sights [91], simplifying to end up as a function of the both the bistatic β and aspect δ angles (defined in Fig. 4.3b), normalised by the wavelength of the signal.

$$f_d = \frac{2V}{\lambda} \cos(\beta/2) \cos(\delta) \quad (5.1)$$

The generated events can then be plotted with these two angles (Fig. 5.13), with randomised events across the entire range of possible cascades investigated. It can be seen that the value of the bistatic angle β of events remains relatively low, with the majority of events lying between 0° and 40° . This is a product of the antenna depth, which sharply reduces the values that β can reach. In terms of the produced Doppler shifts, this then causes the magnitude of the shifts to reduce by a constant factor. On the other hand, we see that the aspect angle δ occupies a wide range of possible angles; using Eq. 5.1, it can be seen that when $\delta = 90^\circ$, no shifts will be produced. If the frequency shifts were solely caused by Doppler shifts, it would then produce a frequency plot akin to the one shown in 5.12, with the shifts described with a gradual distribution - and in this plot, the small area where the no shifts are seen indeed corresponds to events with an aspect angle of $\delta = 90^\circ$. However, for plots with significant contributions from plasma coherence this is no longer the case; therefore, Doppler shifts are surpassed by the effects of plasma coherence, leading to the distinct boundaries of the transmitter frequency regions. Therefore, we cannot solely explain the frequency shifts using the Doppler shift equation, but it does help describe areas

of the polar plot outside of plasma coherence.

Furthermore, this description also provides a useful way to clearly define the boundaries of where the plasma coherence mechanism occurs, achieved by overlaying contours of the aspect angle on the polar plots. To calculate δ for a cascade, a point has to be chosen along the length of the cascade, normally taken at the maximum of the cascade, $\sim 7.5\text{m}$. Previously, we have identified that the coherence mechanism will only occur for the strongest region of the cascade profile, and δ can be retrieved for the boundaries of this region, approximately between 4 and 12m. Using these three points, the events in which $\delta = 90^\circ$ can be found and overlaid on the overview frequency plots. This leads to Fig. 5.14, where it can be seen that the plasma coherence regions are remarkably well described by the arrival directions at which this is true. This can also be applied to the amplitude view, in Fig. 5.15 and leads us the conclusion that the regions in which the coherence mechanism is dominant can be predicted to occur for arrival directions in which the aspect angle - over the strongest region of the cascade - is equal to 90° .

Figure 5.14: Overview at which the aspect angle is equal to 90° , and no frequency shifts are identified, for the frequency polar plots. The aspect angle is retrieved from three points down the length of the cascade (3.5, 7.5, 13)m.

Figure 5.15: Overview at which the aspect angle is equal to 90° , and no frequency shifts are identified, for the amplitude polar plots; the colour scale on the right is set to the peak amplitude [V]. The aspect angle is retrieved from three points down the length of the cascade (3.5, 7.5, 12)m.

In summary, it has been shown that signals with arrival directions that correspond to a particular aspect angle $\delta = 90^\circ$ for the strongest plasma regions exhibit boosted amplitudes and a strong transmit frequency component in their frequency response. The events originating in the plasma coherence region are routinely found to be the strongest signals produced, and it therefore seems reasonable to conclude that this effect may well be identifiable in real radar echo signals. This is a mechanism that has not been identified previously however, and more investigation will be required to conclude this definitively; there may be other factors in realistic signals that obscure this mechanism.

5.2 Cherenkov Effects

In this section, we will address the distinct interference features in the polar plots; the ring and stripes seen in the upper left and upper right of both plots in Fig. 5.1. Examples of individual events taken from inside both features are shown in Fig. 5.16, where very distinct differences can be seen. Furthermore, in the overview plots it is clear that these features appear regularly for nearly all polar plots. In the frequency plots, these represent another area of arrival directions in which the shifts are not well described by the Doppler shift equation. We can therefore surmise that another effect is taking precedence at these arrival directions.

Figure 5.16: Three individual events demonstrating extreme frequency spectra. Event A is strongly upshifted, B is picked from the centre for comparison, and C is strongly downshifted. The phases of both A and C are both relatively decoherent.

Since both features appear curved with respect to either the receiver or transmitter, the opening angles RVP and TVP (defined in Fig. 4.3a) will be used to describe where they appear in the polar plots. In Fig. 5.17, it is clearly shown that these features are found at particular values of these angles, specifically RVP $\sim 56^\circ$ and TVP $\sim 123^\circ$.

Figure 5.17: RVP and TVP angle contours overlaid on the frequency overview, for RVP $\sim 56^\circ$ in solid lines, and TVP $\sim 123^\circ$ in dashed lines. Here, the left half of the plot shows the signal amplitudes and the right half shows the signal frequencies.

At this point, the reader will be referred back to Section 1.1, since features that appear at a consistent opening angle imply the presence of Cherenkov effects, and this can be easily tested using the Cherenkov angle Eq. 1.1. A refractive index of $n = 1.78$, as found in ice, for relativistic motion, produces $\theta_c = 56^\circ$. This is the angle at which the RVP features are found, strongly suggesting that these features are related to Cherenkov effects. This is also the opening angle at which Askaryan radiation from the in-ice cascade would be expected to occur - however, the Askaryan emission mechanism is not included in the MARES calculation, which means that the features present in the polar plots are due to coherence independent of Askaryan radiation. Furthermore, this coherence also takes a different form to the effects found in the plasma coherence region, discussed previously. This can be demonstrated again by exploring the individual waveforms in the effect.

We can select an individual signal from this high frequency ring. In the top event of Fig. 5.16, the waveform is strongly compressed and an extreme frequency shift is visible in the spectrogram. This can be explained by again focusing on the phase of the event. However, now we will look at the shape of the phase plot, specifically the curved front of the plot. Comparing this curve with its constituent waveform, it can be seen that the earliest arrival time of signals from the plasma originate not from the top of the cascade, but halfway down the cascade length. This occurs due to the combination of the relativistic cascade and the non-relativistic signals propagating through the ice, and is purely a function of the detector geometry. There are certain cascade arrival directions in this geometry which cause the detected arrival times of the signal to appear earlier than would be expected in a completely non-relativistic regime.

This can perhaps be best illustrated by qualitatively describing the situation. For an ob-

server positioned at the receiver, the plasma can be approximated to appear instantaneously, due to the relativistic cascade front. Dividing the plasma into segments, each segment will then simultaneously begin to transmit signals towards the observer, travelling at speeds of $v = c/n$, since the ice is already illuminated with radio waves from the CW transmitter. The time taken for the signal from each segment to then reach the observer depends only on the distance of the segment from the receiver.

For arrival directions where the plasma is pointed away from the receiver, the signal that arrives first to the observer will have been emitted from a segment at the top of the trail, corresponding to the shortest distance. However, if the plasma is directed towards the observer, the segment at the shortest distance is instead found at some point down the plasma length; accordingly, the first signal to arrive will have been emitted from this point. If this occurs, it follows that the signal will be seen to arrive faster than expected for a cascade originating at that position. This is illustrated by plotting the first arrival times of all the signals in the polar plots of Fig. 5.1, shown in Fig. 5.18. The bright region in the upper left is the region in which the signals arrive faster than expected, and anywhere outside of this area has a fixed arrival time pointing back to the initial position of the cascade; a signal travel time that can be calculated as $t = c/n \times R_r$. This is useful, as determining the effects that influence arrival times and being able to accurately predict them becomes important for later reconstruction applications.

Figure 5.18: The first arrival times of signals in the polar plot of $(15,20)m$. Any events that occur for an $RVP \leq 56^\circ$ will arrive earlier than expected.

Finally, in this scenario there will be a particular arrival direction with respect to the observer from which the signals from a majority of the segments arrive at the receiver at the same time. This has the effect of producing signals that are strongly compressed, causing the signal frequency at this arrival direction to dramatically increase, as demonstrated for events in Fig. 5.20, and this direction translates to the RVP angle of 56° . Therefore, the ring

of high frequency shifts in the polar plots is produced by time compression of the signals at the Cherenkov angle from the relativistic cascade.

Figure 5.19: Maps showing the arrival directions of the signals selected in Fig. 5.20 (left) and Fig. 5.23 (right).

Figure 5.20: . Four individual signals demonstrating effects found on the ring feature. Their respective arrival directions are shown in Fig. 5.19.

It could be expected that the signal amplitude on a Cherenkov ring would be boosted, as this is a demonstrated effect of coherence. In the amplitude polar plots of Fig. 5.2 however, the ring appears only as a region of disrupted amplitudes. Currently, it is thought that the amplitude of the signal is in fact boosted at this region, but the duration of this increase is on such a short timescale that it is not shown because the sampling rate is too low to capture this effect. It may be possible to capture this effect with MARES, where the sampling ratio can easily be increased, but it is likely beyond what could be sampled in a realistic radar system.

Figure 5.21: Polar plot of Fig. 5.1 at (15,20)m, where the pulse width of each signal is plotted respective to the arrival direction. The lowest widths are found on the Cherenkov ring on the left of the plot.

The Cherenkov ring is also seen in the pulse width of the generated signals. This can be calculated for each signal and plotted, as in Fig. 5.21. The compression effect of the Cherenkov ring are clearly shown, with the shortest signals arriving on the ring itself and longer signals found outside of the ring. This can be shown for randomised data in Fig. 5.22, where a strong correlation is shown between RVP and R_r distance. It has been suggested that this becomes less clearly defined for more realistic signals, where the influence of noise makes it harder to define the pulse width of a signal - but the clear link between the two warrants further investigation, as it could be used to reconstruct signal arrival direction.

Figure 5.22: Pulse width plotted against the RVP angle, with peak frequencies represented on the colour scale. This can be seen as a one-dimensional version of the pulse width polar plot Fig. 5.21. The minimum pulse width corresponds with RVP = 56°.

The angle at which the TVP feature occurs (123°) can be seen as a reflection of the RVP

angle (56°) across 90° , which leads to the conclusion that it represents a form of the same effect. This appears similar to the diffraction effects expected from slit diffraction, with the maximum destructive interference for the signal amplitude found at $\text{TVP} = 123^\circ$. This is demonstrated in Fig. 5.23, where it is clear that the signals are now significantly extended, occasionally to the point that a full oscillation is no longer achieved. This leads to difficulties in the use of FFTs on the signal, and subsequently creates the blank stripes that can be seen in the frequency polar plots for this region. Furthermore, if the transmitter frequency is increased, we see that both of these features are affected (Fig. A.5). The width of the Cherenkov ring decreases for higher frequencies - an effect seen for the Cherenkov rings of askaryan emission [5] and the spacing of the stripes changes, as expected for diffraction effects. Finally, further evidence can also be found in the polar plots with low plasma lifetimes. Here, the two features remain even when the phase coherence is removed. The relativistic motion of the particle cascade remains for these signals, even if the plasma is now very short-lived; consequently, the Cherenkov effects also remain.

Figure 5.23: . Four individual signals picked from the striped low amplitude region. Respective arrival directions can be found in Fig. 5.19.

To conclude, at or near the Cherenkov angle in ice with respect to the receiver (or reflected in the transmitter), we can expect to see extreme upshifting (or downshifting) in the received signal. For example, when plotted against RVP angles, the high frequencies reach a sharp cutoff around 7GHz, which turns out to be the frequency limit from the FFT used. This effect is also seen in the signal amplitude; in the Cherenkov ring, it occurs on such short timescales that it results in a disrupted amplitude, and in the TVP feature the amplitude is strongly suppressed, as the segment contributions destructively interfere. Finally, the Cherenkov effects can also introduce interesting exceptions for both the signal arrival times and pulse widths.

5.3 Summary

In the polar plot overviews of Figures 5.2 and 5.3, we see two main effects, both demonstrating different types of coherence. Plasma coherence boosts the signal amplitude and particular transmitter frequency for favourable arrival directions, and is a product of coherence in the summed electric field at the receiver from each individual section. This link can be demonstrated qualitatively, and the effect may be predicted according to the aspect angle of the arrival direction. The other features have been linked to Cherenkov effects, a by-product of the relativistic speeds of the cascades. This is separate to Askaryan emission that would also be produced by the cascades, but does appear in the same opening angle. It leads to very high frequency band (Cherenkov ring) and very low frequency diffraction stripes. Relativistic motion also produces signatures in the arrival time of the signals (time-compression) and in the pulse width, producing a sharp relation between the opening angle and the width.

The most significant properties found have been detailed in this chapter, but more properties were investigated in the course of this work, which have been shown in Appendix A. To conclude, we can now return to the range of waveforms shown in Fig. 5.5, where we have sufficiently explored the radar echo signal properties to be able to explain the differences seen in the signals of this plot. The highest amplitudes seen in the left of the plot -for a fixed scale - are caused by plasma coherence, found to occur for azimuth angles around both 0° and 180° , boosting the amplitudes by an order of magnitude. To the right of the plot, the signals show noticeably higher frequencies at arrival directions facing towards the antennas, between 180° and 359° azimuth angles, caused by signal Doppler shifting. This is disrupted by the two events at 55° and 270° , at which point Cherenkov effects strongly modify the signal frequencies. Finally, the events within the Cherenkov ring (270° to 330°) appear at earlier times than the other events, due to the relativistic cascades.

Chapter 6

Reconstruction

Having explored a range of signal properties, we can begin to consider their applications in possible reconstruction methods. Work has been previously undertaken into investigating reconstruction methods for RET (e.g [53, 93, 100]), but there are still many areas to explore, especially with the use of MARES signals which have not yet been employed in reconstruction analysis. In this chapter, this is primarily undertaken for events within the RET-CR setup, although the methods investigated will still have some relevance to RET-N; both telescopes utilise the radar echo signal, even though the latter is planned to have more antennas at much deeper depths and different triggering mechanisms.

6.1 Reconstruction Goals

The aim of reconstruction methods using the radar echo signal is to identify the initial energy, the arrival direction and interaction vertex of the event, through the application of the signal properties explored in the previous chapter. In the following section, some methods to obtain these three values are discussed and explored where possible. This does not constitute a comprehensive discussion of reconstruction for RET-CR, but is undertaken in order to demonstrate the reconstruction potential of different properties identified in the course of this work.

6.1.1 Energy

Reconstructing the energy of the progenitor neutrino or CR involves multiple steps, since the target plasma is a secondary or even tertiary product of the particle. First, the energy of the cascade can be retrieved using the strength of the signal detected - which is closely correlated to the cascade energy - after which the initial energy of the progenitor particle can be inferred. This adds an extra complication, as the amount of energy transferred to the cascade that was originally held by the particle has to be determined. In order to retrieve the cascade energy via the strength of the signal in this work, both the position and arrival direction of the event would first have to be established, as the strength of the signal is very dependent on these two parameters. With these two quantities, the energy within the simulation space is then relatively easy to produce, as the signal power and cascade energy are strongly correlated for fixed detector parameters. This is shown in Fig. 6.1, where events with a fixed position and arrival direction - as found in the polar plots - exhibit peak amplitude magnitudes that correlate to the cascade energy.

Figure 6.1: The effect on signal amplitudes for different cascade energies, using fixed positions and arrival directions. The cascade energies shown, from left to right, were 20PeV, 100PeV, 400PeV. The same plots are shown in the appendix in Figures A.9 and A.10, and it is noted here that higher energies have small effects on the location of the Cherenkov effects and the thickness of the coherence region in the polar plots, but the influence of these are very small.

6.1.2 Arrival Direction

Figure 6.2: The peak frequency of respective events plotted against their RVP angles, with TVP angles indicated on the colour scale. The transmitter frequency is indicated with a vertical grey line. Most notable is the large upshift effect at and around an RVP $\sim 56^\circ$, corresponding to the Cherenkov ring. Beyond this, points found at the transmitter frequency of 0.25GHz are largely a function of plasma coherence effects which means they are found for a wide range of RVP angles, and the shifts outside of these two regions are largely produced by Doppler effects.

A key property related to reconstructing event arrival direction is the signal frequency. In the previous section, a range of varied effects in the frequency domain have been shown; Doppler shifts, described with Fig. 5.1, Cherenkov effects and plasma coherence. The final frequency content of an event is a product of all three mechanisms, where one normally takes precedent over the others depending on the arrival direction and position of the event.

This is shown for many randomised signals, plotted with respect to the event RVP, in Fig. 6.2.

It can be seen that a specific frequency value will not correspond to a single RVP solution, but it will considerably narrow the solution space - unless the peak frequency is located at the transmitter frequency. Nevertheless, this issue can be circumvented by using multiple receivers; the probability that all three receivers will see no frequency shifts for one event is very low, and comparing the frequencies retrieved by the receivers will constrain the possible solution space of arrival directions. This is demonstrated in Fig. 6.3, where polar plots are shown corresponding to the three receivers used for a single event. Any events outside of vertical and near-vertical arrival directions are likely to have unique frequency-shift solutions in the three plots. This could also be combined with other properties, such as the pulse width, using the distribution in Fig. 5.22 to obtain a more precise solution.

Figure 6.3: The frequency polar plots for the same position (15,20)m for RX1, RX2 and RX3 (left to right).

It may be possible to perform reconstruction with just a single transmitter-receiver pair, as opposed to multiple receivers, which would allow for increased uptime in the case of an antenna failing. Furthermore, with a significant number of receivers, it could be possible to retrieve arrival direction using relative timing differences. This is a technique often used in optical Cherenkov detectors or surface radio arrays, and could be used if only for an initial fit in RET-N, which is currently aiming to have a number of receivers.

6.1.3 Interaction Vertex

If the positions of the antennas in the detector setup are known to a good level of accuracy, the interaction vertex, or position, can be identified by using the arrival times of the signals in each receiver. This is similar to radar ranging, where the distances to the target are found by recording the signal travel time and converting that to distance with a simple speed-time equation. Since the RET-CR radar system employs CW radar, this is accomplished by making use of the relative timing differences between signals, instead of the full signal travel time.

Compared to RET-N, or other neutrino detectors where cascades could feasibly be produced throughout the detecting volume, RET-CR is somewhat unusual in that there is a fixed plane - corresponding roughly to the ice surface - from which we can expect the cascades to originate from. This fixes the depth of the initial position, leaving only the x and

y positions to be found. There is an added complication though, if we consider the signal of a typical event. For a vertical arrival direction, the earliest signal received will be emitted from the top of the cascade, and if this quantity is used in reconstruction, the produced location will be on this plane of origin. However, the magnitude of the signal at this time is very small, which means that successfully identifying this time in noisy signals will most likely not be possible. While very good position reconstruction can be made in simulation space with the first arrival times, there is not much application for this except to check the validity of methods. Instead, it is more useful to investigate whether the event position can be retrieved from around or at the peak amplitude time of the signal. This is a parameter that we can be reasonably sure of measuring in a real event, even with noise and other factors introduced into the mix. However, the profile of the cascade again has to be considered; the length down the cascade which corresponds to the peak amplitude correlates to the maximum reflecting point of the cascade - $\sim 7.5\text{m}$ for 20PeV cascades - which will appear at different lengths in the frame of reference of each receiver. Additionally, for signals that experience time-compression from relativistic effects, the time at which the signal is received will be earlier than expected. Therefore, the reconstructed property from this quantity will be a point at a particular depth in the ice, corresponding to the strongest reflecting region in the cascade, which will then have to be extrapolated backwards to retrieve the interaction vertex on the ice surface.

It is especially important to reconstruct the event position with reasonable accuracy, since many of the properties described earlier are position-dependent, and to a certain extent the reconstruction of other parameters (energy, arrival direction) may depend on first gaining a position estimate. With this in mind, some time was spent on implementing possible methods to retrieve the position of events.

6.2 Position Reconstruction Methods

The events generated to explore position reconstruction had a fixed energy of 20PeV, no noise was added to any of the produced signals, and the refractive index was kept at a constant value of $n = 1.78$. Within MARES some physical effects are implemented, such as signal attenuation in the ice, which can be expected to marginally degrade reconstruction, but this is only a minor effect. Therefore very good reconstruction should be possible, within the boundaries of the simulation. Consequently, the methods explored within may be less effective for more realistic signals. This will be discussed further, but a full reconstruction analysis constitutes an extensive undertaking currently beyond the scope of this work.

6.2.1 Trilateration

An example event for a detector setup with three receivers (resembling RET-CR, see Sec. 4) is shown in Fig. 6.5. Accordingly, three signals are shown, and the time differences between them correspond to the different travel times - or distances - from the cascade to each receiver.

Figure 6.4: The position $(47,20)$ m of the example event used in the below analysis, with an arrival direction of $(171,108)^\circ$.

Figure 6.5: An example event of Fig. 6.5 as detected in three receivers. Two types of arrival time are marked for all three of the signals; the solid line indicates the first arrival time, and the dotted - dashed line indicates the peak amplitude time.

The first method used was trilateration (or triangulation). This involves creating a volume of different point-positions, encompassing the regions in which cascades are expected to originate from within the detector. For each point in this volume, the expected arrival time for that point is calculated - for each receiver - by the distance between the point and the receiver, converted into a time with the assumed speed of the signal ($v = c/n$).

This was the arrival time calculation initially employed in trilateration, and is still used in the other method investigated. However, it became necessary to modify this calculation for trilateration. Instead, a coordinate square of point-positions was created, on the plane of origin for the signals, which serves as the possible point of origin for each event. This was then extrapolated into three dimensions by following first the path of the cascade into the ice, and then the path of the signal from points down the length of the cascade. This means that two different speeds are combined: the speed of the cascade, taken as ($v = c$) and the speed of the signal ($v = c/n$). Varying the cascade length (l) allows for the entire volume to

be searched, over a range of possible arrival directions at each origin position. The arrival time is given by Eq. 6.1, which simplifies to the simple $t = (n/c)R_r$ for a cascade length of 0m, at the surface. The reason that this modified equation is needed is to properly capture the time-compression of the signal from Cherenkov effects. If this isn't taken into account, the reconstructed positions using this method are uniformly inaccurate by ~ 10 metres or more.

$$t = l/c + (n/c)\sqrt{l^2 + R_r^2 - 2lR_r \cos \text{RVP}} \quad (6.1)$$

The results of trilateration with this timing equation are shown for two arrival times, in Figures 6.6a and 6.6b. As expected, it is shown that the first arrival times originate from the top of the cascade, which is successfully retrieved, while the peak amplitude times reflect the cascade maximum. The latter result is encouraging as it would allow for position reconstruction. However, to implement this, the smallest value retrieved - taken as the best position fit - would ideally be found in the group of positions near the true cascade track. For the current form of this method, this is not the case; it can be seen in the colour scale of Figures 6.6a and 6.6b that the retrieved values are very similar, and the smallest value is then found randomly across the produced curve. It has been suggested that with an improved normalisation of the signals used, it may be possible to change this behaviour so that the smallest value would correspond with the maximum of the cascade. Alternatively, the produced curve could be fit to find the curve minimum. Currently, this method is able to at least visually retrieve the position of the cascade, corresponding to the maximum of the shower, but reliably converting this into a reconstructed position is not yet possible, limiting the discussions that can be made of application of this method. It may be of interest to further exploration however, as it could be possible to also retrieve the arrival direction of the event, by performing trilateration on a range of arrival times taken from different thresholds along the signal.

Figure 6.6: Trilateration performed using two arrival times; the first arrival times (a) and peak amplitude times (b). The track of the event is shown in orange, with the orange dot reflecting the initial cascade position. The marked points represent the smallest values retrieved for each cascade length over the entire search volume, representing the most likely reconstructed position. The colour scale describes the difference between the calculated and the signal times.

6.2.2 Interferometry

The second method investigated was interferometry. Here, the calculated arrival times can be compared to the entirety of the signals received, so that a choice of arrival time is no longer necessary. For a particular point, the expected arrival time at a receiver is subtracted from the measured signal at that receiver, for all three receivers, as in Fig. 6.7. If this is done for every possible position, the point at which the signals best align should then reflect origin position of the signal.

Figure 6.7: The signals of the event in Fig. 6.5, resampled on the same time axis and shifted corresponding to the true position of the event, causing them to align reasonably well.

It is necessary then to create a measurement of the alignment between signals. For example, in [57] a method is employed that first cross-correlates a template to each signal, after which the transformed signals are multiplied and summed with each other. This works well, but is largely possible because the frequencies of the in-ice Askaryan signals only vary slightly

across parameters. In contrast, the generated radar echoes within exhibit significantly different frequencies depending on their arrival direction relative to the measuring receiver, which could present an issue in choosing a template that would apply to each signal, and currently this was not employed. Another possible method is summing the signals and then retrieving the peak amplitude, or power of the produced signal sum, as described in [101], although this may also be complicated by the signal frequency variation. To investigate different possible methods, a sample of those explored are shown in Fig. 6.8.

Figure 6.8: Different correlation methods compared, for one event. Values are sampled down the length of the cascade, and it would be expected for the highest value to be returned near the strongest region of the cascade, between 5 and 10m. Hil.sum and sum both add the shifted waveforms, with the former first using a Hilbert transform on each signal. Power is found by integrating the summed signal, and normalising by the duration. CC and CCn both employ a form of cross-correlation wherein the signals are first multiplied with each other before being summed, and the latter first normalises each signal before multiplying them.

Figure 6.9: Interferometry performed on the example event. In (a), Hilbert transforms are applied to the signals which are then summed, and in (b), the power of the sum of the signals is retrieved. The colour scale of (a) is omitted since the value of each position was found to be approximately constant, and in (b) the power is plotted, where a higher colour indicates a position with more likelihood of the true event position.

Assuming that a good method for correlation has been picked, this can then be applied to a

range of points over a coordinate grid, to find the highest values over all possible locations. An example event is shown in Figures 6.9a and 6.9b, for the Hil.sum and power methods described above. Again, the produced curve has a minimum at the point closest to the true event track down the length of the cascade. This would be expected, as the returned position will be largely influenced by the portion of the signal around the peak amplitude time, the strongest part of the signal.

Figure 6.10: The perpendicular distance of the chosen positions from the true track of the event shown in Fig. 6.9b, calculated for the depth of the ice. A smaller distance corresponds to more accurate reconstruction.

Quantitative analysis of the accuracy of these reconstruction methods has not yet been performed, but an estimate can be found by plotting the perpendicular distances between each reconstructed positions and the true track, as shown in Fig. 6.10. Using this estimate, the interferometry method - this time employing the normalised cross-correlation shown in Fig. 6.8 - can then be applied to a large dataset of vertical cascades, with the results plotted as the average distance retrieved for the whole cascade for each position: this is shown in Fig. 6.11, providing an estimate overview of the reconstruction accuracy across the detector setup.

The retrieved distances are generally low, with some scattered exceptions - at these events, the reconstruction largely fails, leading to very high distances. The cause of this is yet to be ascertained, but appears stronger for events close to the transmitter, a region in which reconstruction could be hindered. There are also three distinct regions behind each receiver where the reconstruction is uniformly worse - this likely reflects a different region of the radar system, the forward scattering region [91]. In general however, the technique provides satisfactory position reconstruction, with the average distance found to be slightly higher than 1m.

Figure 6.11: Total distances for a uniform event dataset of vertical cascades with interferometry and (normalised) cross-correlation. Antennas are indicated with triangle markers, and the colour scale is set to the average perpendicular distance of each position from the true cascade track.

Interferometry proved easier to run in a cluster environment, allowing for this wider analysis to be completed. If the method were to be further investigated, it would have to be significantly optimised as it currently requires a large amount of computation time. Furthermore, neither interferometry or trilateration currently return a single position value that is accurate, despite visually reconstructing the cascade position, hindering assessment of the reconstruction accuracy. Another area of interest would be in the effect of arrival directions on the reconstruction. Initial exploration of this hinted that there would be a decrease in accuracy for inclined cascades, and that many of the methods in Fig. 6.8 were much less effective for signals that displayed strong frequency shifts. A possible way to explore this, following the signal properties methods, would be to perform the reconstruction on the polar plots in the overview maps, which would provide a clear visual demonstration of the interplay between reconstruction accuracy and different signal mechanisms.

6.3 Summary

In general, this chapter has shown that the position of the events can be satisfactorily reconstructed with just the relative arrival times of signals. From this, the arrival direction can be retrieved using the wide range of frequency shifts, after which the energy can be found from the signal amplitude. Obtaining more conclusive results from this analysis is not currently possible, largely due to time constraints, but possible applications of signal properties for reconstruction have been demonstrated. The aim has also been to convey the wide potential found in the radar echo signals for reconstruction, of which only a small aspect have been explored here.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

7.1 Discussion

The goal of this work was to investigate properties of the radar echo signal, looking in particular for features that could be utilised in reconstruction methods, and accordingly a wide range of signal properties have been explored in this work. Ideally, a more quantitative analysis would have been completed, if only to aid later discussions and assess implications of the findings. This would also help formulate more rigorous descriptions of the properties and the areas for which they can be predicted to appear in different signals; currently, this relies largely on qualitative descriptions of the detector setup and cascades within. Furthermore, this exploration was undertaken in a limited portion of the full phase space, in order for possible findings to remain applicable to the RET-CR deployment. This could have been extended, to check for additional effects not present in this range of the phase space, or to test the extent to which the identified effects remain consistent over the full range of possible signals. However, this work was undertaken simultaneously with the MSc student Jannes Loonen (Vrije Universiteit Brussel), who did investigate the full phase space in the course of his work, leading to more confidence in the universality of the conclusions within.

More specific improvements could have been made in the time-frequency analysis, where issues were encountered in the use of FFTs and spectrograms to obtain the peak frequency of a signal. Ideally, the peak frequency of the signal would be obtained via the spectrogram, because it provides a more complete representation of the frequency content. However, the code required to implement this can quickly become complicated, as the highest value must be retrieved from a 2D image that often exhibits complex patterns. Furthermore, the generation of the spectrogram would first have to be significantly optimised; currently each image takes a minute to be produced, which would quickly create a bottleneck in the analysis of larger datasets. Both of these issues can be overcome, and for a full quantitative analysis should definitely be considered. However, this was not achieved in this work, and the FFT method was mainly used instead to determine frequency content. This served the purposes of the analysis performed within, except for extremely downshifted signals and for the more complex frequency spectra, with diffraction fringes or broad upshifts. In the circumstance that the spectrogram or FFT of an event displays an upshifted fringe pattern, as in Fig. 7.1, there will often be multiple peaked contributions to the frequency; the question then, is which one of these peaks should be taken as the peak frequency, if they are approximately equal in magnitude. In this scenario, choosing a peak frequency value serves as a less useful

estimate for the true content found in the signal, not properly capturing the layers of structure that may be present.

Figure 7.1: An example spectrogram displaying broad upshifts. From a position of $(15,20)m$, and arrival direction of $(153,305)^\circ$.

Assessing the applicability of this study is made more difficult by it remaining mainly in simulation space; there are a range of factors that would have to be considered when trying to evaluate how signal properties may appear in real data, and to what extent they could be recorded. No noise was applied to signals, which would appear in real signals, and could lead to a lower amount of information retrieved on the signal properties. Furthermore, the ice in MARES was set at a constant refractive index, while real ice is full of impurities, dust and bubbles, which can have a scattering effect on the radio signal, especially in the upper regions of the ice monitored by RET-CR, where the refractive index is much more variable. A full development of reconstruction methods and signals would likely necessitate some form of ray tracing, to properly develop an understanding of other factors including refraction of the signals and reflections. The length scales of RET-CR are small, so the strength of the signals is high enough that diffraction and refraction effects may not play a huge role, but there could, for example, be a signal contribution from reflections off the ice surface. All of these contributing effects leads to challenges in conclusively determining the application of this work. However, it was largely motivated by the need to gain a greater understanding of the signal itself, which would have been complicated by the addition of the large array of relevant additional factors. Now that a better understanding has been achieved, the applicability of the findings can be investigated as an extension to this work.

A preliminary exploration of reconstruction was performed, with the implementation of two methods for finding cascade positions. Only the signal arrival times were utilised for this, while it has been shown that there are many remaining avenues to explore. The methods described in this work may have gained more reliability if they had all been demonstrated to some degree, instead of just position reconstruction. In this scenario, a more complete analysis of the methods could have been undertaken, in order to gain an insight into the accuracy of the reconstruction, even if only applied to simulation space signals. The lack of more realistic signals also affects the analysis of the reconstruction methods considered, since it becomes hard to draw wide conclusions on reconstruction without adding realistic signals. This is well illustrated by frequency; a wide range of frequency shifts have been

spotted to occur, reaching up to and beyond several GHz. However, in practice it may be hard to detect these frequency shifts, as we are limited by antenna designs that can feasibly be implemented in ice. Properly evaluating the applicability of frequency to any reconstruction methods then requires a fuller account of physical effects and technological constraints, which begins to represent a full separate study, beyond the limits of this work.

7.1.1 Future Work

The course of the work completed over the last year in this thesis represents the beginning of possible investigations that can be performed with MARES in this area. There are a lot of remaining areas to explore, as well as potential applications that can be studied. Here, we will discuss some of these possibilities.

- *Plasma coherence.* This is a mechanism that had not been identified before the work undertaken within; accordingly, there is still more to investigate. This includes rigorously defining the full limits of the effect, assessing how it will appear in more realistic signals if possible, and exploring whether it can be used in reconstruction. For example, it can be seen in Fig. A.15 that increasing the transmitter frequency leads to a sharper and more compact region of phase coherence, which would imply that the produced amplitude boost will be reduced in size. However, in Figures A.5 and A.6, it is shown that this is not the case - in fact, the extent of the boosted region appears to increase. This is an example of an interesting intricacy in the produced signal which is currently not as well understood, but could be with further investigation.
- *Askaryan radiation.* The expected overlap between the Cherenkov effects identified within and Askaryan radiation is currently unknown, and how these mechanisms would appear together, or if they could be disentangled and detected may be hard to answer without simulations. Investigating this could be undertaken with a form of extension to MARES in order to also simulate the Askaryan effect. Alternatively, code packages and simulations of Askaryan radiation from neutrino cascades have been explored in other work, largely for in-ice Askaryan detectors (e.g [102]) and there may be a way to make use of these to better explore this topic. This would also be of interest for RET-CR, since it is possible that Askaryan radiation from the secondary CR air showers could be found in the experiment [103].
- *Reconstruction methods.* This is another area in which there is still many aspects to investigate and consider, especially with the implementation of more realistic signals. For example, there are certain RET-CR parameters such as antenna depth, and transmit frequency that have been shown to influence the radar echo signal, and understanding the consequences of these on subsequent reconstruction methods can help support different choices for the detector setup used, such as the number of antennas needed in the ice or the transmitter frequency range. Furthermore, both the reconstruction methods investigated used Cartesian coordinates and sampled over depth; swapping to a different coordinate system may expose different strengths or weaknesses for the methods, and may be better suited to the problem. It could also save computation time; in cylindrical coordinates, expected arrival times are symmetrical around each receiver, so positions only have to be calculated for the position depth and height, which could be important in the application of ray tracing. In truth, this

item could have had a list of its own, as reconstruction methods can be fascinatingly involved, despite being built off of basic principles, with techniques slowly refined over years of work.

- *Cascade length.* Success was found in this work in describing signal responses in terms of bistatic radar angles and related terminology, but attempts were hindered by not properly considering cascade lengths in the analysis. Instead, this was estimated using individual points down the cascade, but the effects seen were a combination of many different points weighted according to the region of highest reflecting power in the plasma, and fully describing and predicting signal properties likely requires for this to be properly accounted for. If this is done, known radar features that were visible in the signals but not well described can also be further investigated; the interplay between Cassini ovals and isorange contours, the bistatic and aspect angle, and a more accurate application of the Doppler shift equation. If properly described in simulations, there is potential to apply this understanding to real data, perhaps even benefiting reconstruction efforts.

Listed above are the items which are likely to be of more importance in future work. Beyond this, there are a few areas which warrant further investigation, but are likely to have less consequences on future analysis. This includes finding a more comprehensive way to display signal properties for both cascade positions and arrival directions. In this work, the overview polar plots were used for this (e.g. Fig. 5.2), but the number of positions that can be sampled are limited by the size of the polar plots. This serves the purpose of the analysis within, and the overview plots have been very beneficial in understanding the radar echo scatter - but if anyone has successfully reached this point in the thesis and has any ideas for a more complete overview, they are very welcome to reach out.

7.2 Outlook

Reaching a good understanding of how the properties of the radar echo signal change with respect to different cascade and antenna parameters is important, if the signal is to be utilised to detect in-ice cascades and their progenitors, with RET-N and RET-CR. Successfully detecting radar echo signals and reconstructing properties of the cosmic rays means that the radar echo method can be validated in-situ, and then applied to the main goal of RET-N, where detections of UHE neutrinos allow for unique insights into the high-energy astrophysical processes described all the way back in Chapter 2.

The task of investigating the signal properties was approached by using a mapping method to gain overviews of different properties for different cascade and detector parameters. Common features seen in these overviews were then further explored with individual signals and properties of the plasma and cascades themselves, which were used to identify the mechanisms behind the features. With this method, the plasma coherence mechanism was found, causing the signal amplitude at particular geometries to be boosted, as well as a higher transmitter frequency contribution to the signal frequency. Outside of these regions, Doppler shifting takes over with the exceptions caused by Cherenkov effects from the relativistic cascade, creating a Cherenkov ring of very high frequencies and disrupted amplitudes, as well as diffraction effects of low amplitudes and frequencies, both found at consistent transmitter

and receiver opening angles.

The combination of these mechanisms produces distinctive effects in the radar echo signals. Combined with radar detection techniques and insights from other astroparticle experiments, this leads to a wide pool of potential reconstruction methods in order to find the progenitor energy, arrival direction and position. Some of these techniques have been discussed, and since many of them depend on initial position determination, two techniques that provide this information are investigated in more detail: trilateration and interferometry, the latter especially providing relatively good reconstruction.

Figure 7.2: The 2024 RET-CR deployment, showing the central solar panel array and DAQ. Picture provided by Steven Prohira, taken by staff at the Greenland Summit Station.

We began this work with a diagram of RET-CR (Fig. 1.1), and therefore we will conclude with a picture of RET-CR in its current deployment, in Fig. 7.2. The experiment will continue observing until late August, after which the data retrieved can be analysed and will hopefully exhibit radar echo signals. This would be a huge step forward in the development of RET-N, and would also provide the opportunity to compare the findings of this thesis to the measured signals themselves, representing an exciting extension of the analysis within. For now, we will have to wait and see what can be found from the measurements of RET-CR.

Appendix A

Extended Analysis

A.1 Further Signal Properties

A complete overview of the effect of different parameters on polar plots is shown here. Each polar plot is positioned at $(15,20)\text{m}$, unless otherwise specified, and both the amplitude and frequency of the signals are displayed. Neither the gain and transmitter power are shown, as they have no visible effect on the signal amplitudes apart from a uniform increase in magnitude.

A.1.1 Antenna Distance

At increased distances from the antennas, observed effects become generally become narrower. This is not significantly demonstrated in the overview plots, as they do not have a large enough extent for this to be seen. Therefore, it is shown here in Fig. A.1 and Fig. A.2, for amplitude and frequency. The shape of the Cherenkov features begin to clearly reflect each other, as the transmitter and receiver appear closer together in the reference frame of the cascade. At a certain distance, monostatic radar geometry will be achieved. Furthermore, the magnitude of the frequency shifts increase and the distinct regions disappear; the cascades appear more as point-targets than lengths with significant dimensions, and the arrival directions for which plasma coherence occurs are reduced.

Figure A.1: Amplitude polar plots sampled with increasing distances from the antennas. The reference plot is shown at $(15,20)\text{m}$ (left), followed by a plot at $(15,50)\text{m}$ (middle) and a plot at $(15,150)\text{m}$.

Figure A.2: Frequency polar plots sampled with increasing distances from the antennas. The reference plot is shown at $(15,20)m$ (left), followed by a plot at $(15,50)m$ (middle) and a plot at $(15,150)m$.

A.1.2 Antenna Depth

The depth of the transmitter and receiver are important for determining the region of the cascade that will be observed. This is demonstrated for amplitude and frequency in Figures A.3 and A.4. For the polar plot at a depth of 10m, a large amount of the signals found within the zenith angle range of 180° to 150° - corresponding to favourable arrival directions for the percentage of energy transferred into the ice from an EAS - are boosted by plasma coherence. As the antenna depth increases, the geometry of the detector changes and this is no longer true. At a depth of 20m, the Cherenkov ring appears much closer to vertical cascades. If we were to make an amplitude overview for antennas at this depth, this would likely play a large role in the produced effects - although it can also be seen that the width of the ring decreases with depth.

Figure A.3: Amplitude polar plots with the antenna (transmitter and receiver) depth increased, fixed at $(15,20)m$. From left to right, the depths are sampled at 10m, 15m and 20m.

Figure A.4: Frequency polar plots with the antenna (transmitter and receiver) depth increased, fixed at (15,20)m. From left to right, the depths are sampled at 10m, 15m and 20m.

A.1.3 Transmitter Frequency

The scattering of the plasma depends on both the plasma frequency and the frequency of the incident transmitter signal. A higher frequency signal therefore penetrates deeper into the plasma, and accordingly the dimensions become less significant, appearing closer to a thin wire. In the MARES maps within, it also plays a large role in the generated interference patterns displayed. The amplitude and frequency polar plots for increasing transmitter frequencies are displayed in Figures A.5 and A.6. It can be seen that the Cherenkov effects vary; the ring reduces in width, and the diffraction pattern significantly reduces in size. Furthermore, stronger interference can be identified in the left of the plot, beginning to override the Cherenkov ring. However, the plasma coherence region remains the same size, with more distinct regions and slightly higher amplitudes in the lower part of each plot. This is perhaps unexpected, and may require further investigation.

Figure A.5: Amplitude polar plots for increasing transmitter frequency, at an antenna depth of 10m. From left to right: 0.25GHz, 0.5GHz, 0.75GHz.

Figure A.6: Frequency polar plots for increasing transmitter frequency, at an antenna depth of 10m. From left to right: 0.25GHz, 0.5GHz, 0.75GHz. Accordingly, the value found in each central band increases, which is shown in the colour change. It can also be seen that the peak frequency method begins to behave differently for higher transmitter frequencies. This was concluded to be a symptom of the complex frequency responses of the signals, reducing the applicability of the peak frequency value.

A.1.4 Polarisation

The antenna polarisation can be set to three values; X, Y and Z, corresponding to Cartesian axes. Modifying this polarisation can have surprising effects on the produced position maps, and the polar plots of the three polarisations are shown in Figures A.7 and A.8, for amplitude and frequency. Notably, the Cherenkov effects in all three remain fixed. The Y polarized plot shows the largest differences, with an additional distorted low-amplitude ring, and an adjustment so that the highest amplitudes in the plot are now found to be in the centre of the plasma coherence region, and not the top.

Figure A.7: Amplitude polar plots with varied polarisation. From left to right; Z, Y, X. All the plots in the chapters of this work use a polarisation of Z (vertical).

Figure A.8: Frequency polar plots with varied polarisation. From left to right; Z, Y, X.

A.1.5 Energy

The energy of the cascades was investigated in very early stages of the analysis, and concluded to have no effect on the signal properties - in fact, the picture is a little more complex. At antenna depths of 10m, larger energies do not produce wholly different effects, as seen in Figures A.9 and A.10. The larger energies lead to longer shower profiles, but at the energies investigated within the strongest region of the plasma is already located very close to the antenna depths, and small changes of this property therefore would not lead to significant changes. However, if this length is moved, we can expect that the location of the Cherenkov effects will also move - not because the angles in question will change, but because the cascade length at which the estimates have to be made will move with the longer cascade profiles. This is seen in the polar plots, on top of a subtle broadening of the phase coherence region, likely corresponding to a larger range of cascade lengths at which phase coherence can be reached. Furthermore, at different antenna depths a changing energy can be expected to have a more significant effect.

Figure A.9: Amplitude polar plots with varied cascade energies. From left to right; 20PeV, 200PeV, 400PeV.

Figure A.10: Frequency polar plots with varied cascade energies. From left to right; 20PeV, 200PeV, 400PeV.

A.1.6 Refractive Index

Only changing the refractive index parameter without adjusting other medium-specific variables means that the medium has not truly been adjusted. However, this does provide an alternative method to investigate Cherenkov effects; the angle at which we can expect to see them is a function of the medium refractive index. This is demonstrated in Figures A.11 and A.12. As expected, the location of the effects are noticeably moved by this. Both the Cherenkov ring and diffraction stripes also become significantly less wide, with the stripes almost disappearing completely. However the phase coherence region stays constant, unaffected by a changing refractive index.

Figure A.11: Amplitude polar plots with varied refractive indexes. From left to right; 1.78, 1.5, 1.3.

Figure A.12: Frequency polar plots with varied refractive indexes. From left to right; 1.78, 1.5, 1.3.

A.1.7 Plasma Lifetime

The plasma lifetime parameter has been detailed in Chapter 5. Here, a larger range of plasma lifetimes are shown, in Figures A.13 and A.14. Noticeably, the Cherenkov effects remain unaffected for all lifetimes, except for the peak frequencies, which become disrupted. This is attributed to error from the peak frequency analysis, which ran into issues for signals of particularly large length, as generated by longer plasma lifetimes. Meanwhile the plasma coherence region becomes sharper and a little stronger - although this effect is limited, and for larger plasma lifetimes the maps remain largely the same.

Figure A.13: Amplitude polar plots with varied plasma lifetimes. From left to right; 1ns, 10ns, 100ns. The reference plot here is in the centre of the three, not the left.

Figure A.14: Frequency polar plots with varied plasma lifetimes. From left to right; 1ns, 10ns, 100ns.

A.1.8 Phase plots

In Fig. A.15 a selection of phase plots are shown for different plasma lifetimes and transmitter frequencies, which create noticeably different phases. The plasma lifetime phase plot is unexpected; a longer lifetime means that the plasma will survive longer, but it can be clearly seen why very long signals are found at high lifetimes. Furthermore, the amplitude is not increased more, possibly because the maximum coherence is reached, and cannot increase beyond a certain lifetime. The transmitter frequency plots demonstrate increased phase oscillation, with the lengths where coherence is reached beginning to stand out as an optical illusion. It should be noted that the coherence region of the length appears to decrease for higher transmitter frequencies.

Figure A.15: Phase plots for different plasma lifetimes and transmitter frequencies. On the left, plasma lifetimes are adjusted; moving from the top downwards, 1ns, 10ns and 100ns are shown. On the right, 0.25GHz, 0.5GHz and 0.75GHz are shown.

A.2 Position, Antenna Depth and Transmitter Frequency

We will end this section with the following position plots, wherein the transmitter frequency and antenna depth are modified, in Figures A.16 and A.17. All the events are vertical cascades, and along the horizontal axis the transmitter frequency is increased, and along the vertical cascade the antenna depth is increased. The top two rows of positions remain firmly within the phase coherence region, leading to boosted, steady amplitudes that differ only for events near the antenna regions. For these depths, this is the angle at which the Cherenkov effects occur, and it can be seen that as antenna depth is increased the ring moves outwards, until it becomes easy to see. This also begins to correspond to depths where not all events

remain in phase coherence, and instead we start to see lower amplitudes, demonstrated more clearly in Fig. A.4.

The plots found in the bottom right region of Figures A.16 and A.17 display some particularly interesting interference effects, that appear to reflect a combination of known radar effects; Cassini ovals (Fig. A.18a) and isorange contours (Fig. A.18b). It was thought that these would also be present in the position plots at smaller antenna depths (say 10m), but that they are obscured since the antennas are positioned so closely to the strongest regions of the plasma, and therefore dominated by plasma coherence. However, in Fig. A.19, three position plots are shown, picked from the top left, bottom left, and bottom right of Fig. A.17. Below each, the identical plot is shown with a plasma lifetime of $\tau = 0.1ns$. Therefore, this suggests that removing plasma coherence from the picture also removes the radar interference patterns, implying that the latter is caused by the former. To properly understand the mechanisms producing this, a more complete description of radar parameters within the detector will be needed. However, it provides a good point on which to conclude, clearly demonstrating that there is still much more to be investigated with MARES and radar echo signals.

Figure A.16: Position plots for vertical cascades. From left to right, the transmitter frequency is varied (0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.25)GHz, and from top to bottom the antenna depth is varied (10,13,15,17,20)m. Each individual plot is shown with the x axis on the bottom, from -15 to 15m, and the y axis on the left, from -5 to 35m.

Figure A.17: Position plots for vertical cascades, with normalised amplitudes for better comparison of features. From left to right the transmitter frequency is varied (0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.25)GHz, and from top to bottom the antenna depth is varied (10,13,15,17,20)m.

Figure A.18: In (a), cassini ovals are shown, retrieved by multiplying the receiver and transmitter ranges ($R_r R_t$). In (b), isorange contours are shown, retrieved by summing the ranges ($R_r + R_t$).

Figure A.19: Position plots with modified plasma lifetimes. The position plots are chosen for three parameters, and the equivalent plots with low plasma lifetimes (0.1 ns) are shown beneath, for comparison.

Appendix B

Research Data Management

The MARES code package is freely accessible¹ and all the data used within was generated with it. This data is currently stored on the Coma computing cluster of the Radboud Astrophysics department, and for now will be maintained there indefinitely. Signal analysis of the data was performed using Python, primarily with the Numpy [104], Matplotlib [105] and Scipy [106] packages, and this analysis code is also stored on the Coma cluster. The parameters for the data generated and analysis methods employed have been detailed within.

¹<https://github.com/radarEchoTelescope>

Appendix C

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